

D2.3

A harmonized set of life cycle impact assessment methods, with additional temporal differentiation

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACCRONYMS	DESCRIPTION
AoCs	Area of concern
AoPs	Areas of protection
AWARE	Available WAtER REmaining
BbS	Bio-based systems
CFs	Characterization factors
CTUe	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems
CTUh	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans
DALYs	Disability-Adjusted Life Years
DLCA	Dynamic life cycle assessment
DLCIA	Dynamic Life cycle impact assessment
EF	Environmental footprint
ES	Ecosystem services
EP	Environmental Performance
EPD	Ecosystem Damage Potential
EPS	Environmental Priority Strategies
GLAM	Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators
ILCD	International Reference Life Cycle Data System
LANCA	Land Use Indicator Value Calculation
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LUC	Land Use Change
NMVOG	Non-methane volatile organic compounds
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEFCRs	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules
PDF	Potentially Disappeared Fraction
pLCA	Prospective life cycle assessment
SSPs	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
S-LCA	Social-Life Cycle Assessment
TH	Time horizon

PROJECT INFORMATION

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BIO based systems

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5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
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7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
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Period:	PR1
WP:	WP2 Improved methodologies for environmental sustainability and circularity assessment of bio-based systems (bbs)
Task:	T2.3 Harmonization of life cycle impact assessment methods
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Abstract:	<p>The lack of harmonization among LCIA methods significantly reduces transparency and reproducibility in LCA studies, creating barriers for stakeholders aiming to verify, compare, or build upon assessment results. Task 2.3 addresses this challenge by providing a structured synthesis and review of the most relevant LCIA methods and impact categories for bio-based systems, specifically toxicity, water use, land use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. To support harmonization, we apply a method based on a multi-criteria scoring approach (based on the ILCD approach) that evaluates each LCIA method according to seven key criteria: completeness of scope, scientific robustness, relevance to bio-based systems, certainty, transparency, applicability, and level of acceptance. A set of LCIA methods was assessed, drawing on existing characterization models evaluated in prior EU-funded projects. The second part focuses on temporal considerations in LCIA methods, recognizing their particular importance for bio-based systems due to time-sensitive processes. Temporal differentiation was analysed using a dynamic model applied to seven representative bio-based chemicals, based on the methodology developed by INSA (Shimako et al., 2017) adapted to both USEtox and Environmental Footprint toxicity models and parameter data. This modelling explores how human and ecotoxicity impact characterization changes over time. In parallel, a bibliographic review was conducted to evaluate the integration of temporal aspects across other categories. The review highlights current methodological advances as well as gaps in how LCIA methods address temporal dynamics in land use, water use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. Together, this harmonization and temporal differentiation effort provides a consolidated list of suitable LCIA methods and a framework for understanding how impact can evolve over time. The findings are intended to guide future applications of LCA in the bioeconomy, supporting more accurate, consistent, and time-resolved assessments of environmental impacts.</p>

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1 INTRODUCTION

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) follows four phases: defining the goal and scope, compiling the life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impacts assessment (LCIA), and interpreting results. LCIA translates emissions and resource use into environmental indicators (i.e., impacts) using models. Since the 1990s, many LCIA methods have been developed, making comparisons difficult. Two LCAs evaluating similar products may produce significantly different outcomes caused not by actual environmental performance differences, but by methodological inconsistencies (European Commission, 2011).

Harmonization reduces this "methodological noise" and supports credible, meaningful comparisons. **Harmonization of Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) Methods in LCA** refers to the process of aligning and standardizing the various approaches used to evaluate environmental impacts within LCA. The goal is to ensure that results are consistent, comparable, and scientifically robust across studies, regions, and sectors. Specifically, harmonization in LCIA includes the following elements:

- **Fixing Impact Categories:** Ensuring that key environmental impact categories—such as climate change, toxicity, water use, and land use—are clearly defined and consistently included across different LCIA methods.
- **Aligning Characterization Models:** Using common scientific models to convert emissions or resource use into environmental impacts (e.g., converting CO₂ emissions into global warming potential), with consistent units, spatial/temporal scales, and system boundaries.
- **Ensuring Consistent Data and Assumptions:** Aligning underlying datasets, such as background databases and characterization factors, so that differences in results reflect true performance variations, not inconsistencies in input data.
- **Facilitating Comparability:** Harmonized methods make it possible to reliably compare LCA results across studies and sectors—essential for policymaking, product labelling, and industry benchmarking.

Efforts to harmonize LCIA methods include initiatives such as the ILCD Handbook and the Environmental Footprint (EF) method developed by the European Commission (European Commission, 2011), as well as global efforts led by the UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative (Haes et al., 2002). Beyond harmonization, a key limitation of many LCIA methods is the lack of a temporal dimension. LCAs are typically conducted without time-based differentiation, as ISO 14040–44 does not require it. Most LCIA approaches rely on steady-state models and time-integrated indicators. However, incorporating temporal dynamics could significantly influence LCA outcomes and decision-making (Pigné et al., 2020).

This report presents recommended methods for each impact category at the midpoint level, starting with a pre-selection of existing methods and definition of classification criteria. It then evaluates the role of temporal aspects across impact categories, using a dynamic model for toxicity and a literature review on recent advances in land use, water use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services.

Brief definition of key concepts:

Midpoint and Endpoint categories: Midpoints represent specific environmental problems, such as climate change, acidification, and water depletion, while endpoints aggregate these into broader damage categories, e.g., human health, ecosystem quality, and resource scarcity.

Characterization factor (CFs): numerical value (factor) used to convert an environmental input or emission into a potential impact within a specific impact category, typically expressed per unit mass.

Area of Protection (AoP): conceptual endpoint in LCA that represents what we ultimately want to protect. It helps link environmental impacts (like greenhouse gas emissions or toxic releases) to their broader consequences for the environment, human health, or resources.

Impact category: focuses on a specific type of environmental concern, such as climate change, acidification, or human toxicity.

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1.1 Overview of Task 2.3: Review and Harmonization Framework

The first step of Task 2.3 involves a synthesis and review of existing frameworks and indicators for key impact categories in LCA, namely biodiversity, air, water, and soil quality, as well as land and water resource use.

This review focuses on the most recent development in LCIA methods and incorporates findings from EU-funded projects such as ORIENTING, CALIMERO (coordinated by CTA, WP led by LIST), ALIGNED (coordinated by AAU) and GLAM.

The next phase involves comparing state-of-the-art alternatives and integrating them into a harmonized set of LCIA methods. This process identifies existing gaps and limitations, with proposed solutions tailored for feasibility and relevance, particularly in relation to elementary flows significant for Bio-based Systems (BbS) and related products. The LCIA method screening is based on the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) (European Commission, 2011), to develop a coherent and consistent analysis of existing characterisation models, factors and insights.

The harmonization effort will ultimately result in operational LCIA approaches, including a coherent set of CFs for elementary flows commonly found in global databases like EXIOBASE and ecoinvent. In addition, improvements in temporal differentiation of impact assessment are explored, for example, time-dynamic modeling of toxicity impacts (as done by INSA, Shimako et al. (2017)), as well as prospective climate change impact (addressed in T3.3) and future water scarcity modelling (e.g., LIST's work by Baustert et al. (2022)).

Finally, our harmonization covers impact assessment for biodiversity, land use, water use, and air/water/soil quality, including forward-looking impact modelling under future scenarios. This is demonstrated through bio-based chemicals as study in the validation phase for toxicity assessment.

1.2 Objectives of this report

This guidance document presents recommendations on the methods to apply for modelling of the most common categories for bio-based systems. Based on the work of Task 2.3, the recommendations are based on:

- I. The analysis of existing relevant life cycle impact assessment approaches, which is developed in section 2, through the analysis of the main projects relative to bio-based systems and more used methods in LCIA.
- II. A harmonization through selection, aggregation and/or improvement of these. Section 3 describes the selection methodology and criteria for each impact category.
- III. A set of characterization factors or models belonging to the latter, which is described at the end of sections 2 and 3.
- IV. A further improved temporally differentiated characterization impact modelling applied for the toxicity category and further explained in section 4.
- V. An associated set of prospective characterization factors or models. Conventional and prospective characterization factors and models may also be provided in code or excel lists, compatible with LCA software, described at the end of section 4.

2 ANALYSIS OF EXISTING RELEVANT LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT APPROACHES

Each life cycle impact category was evaluated based on recommendations from well-established environmental accounting projects, methodologies, and guidance documents. Methodological guidance was specifically applied to four very common impact categories: toxicity, land use, water use, and biodiversity, including considerations of ecosystem services. It encompasses two sections: 2.1. Existing projects with LCIA development related to Bio-based systems and 2.2 Preselected (most used in LCA studies) LCIA methods.

2.1 Description of projects with LCIA development related to Biobased systems

2.1.1 GLAM project

GLAM (Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators) is an initiative of the United Nations Environmental Programme (see link: [GLAM](#)), with the aim of enhancing global consensus on environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators, generating tangible and practical recommendations for different environmental indicators and characterization factors used in LCIA (Frischknecht & Jolliet, Olivier, 2016). GLAM is funded by the Life Cycle Initiative funding partners, specific contributions from the Swiss, French, and German Governments and is supported by the in-kind contribution from more than 200 scientists.

The overall Goal of GLAM is to establish a comprehensive, consistent and global Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Method, covering classification, characterization, normalization and weighting to assess the life-cycle impacts of products and services on human health, ecosystem quality and natural resources.

Building on the consensual work on life cycle impact assessment since its launch in 2002, the Life Cycle Initiative started GLAM in 2013. The work has been co-led by the University of Michigan, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) and Denmark's Technical University (DTU) and has benefited from the collaboration of hundreds of scientists from across the world. This international expert task force prepares recommendations on the individual topic areas. Progress is reviewed in stakeholder engagement events and expert consultation workshops. The mix of participants consists of a balance of domain experts from five topical tracks: LCIA method developers, providers of life cycle thinking studies (primarily consultants and industry associations), and users of life cycle information, including governmental and intergovernmental organizations, industry, NGOs, and academics.

The GLAM method categorizes environmental impacts into following main Areas of Protection (AoPs):

- Ecosystem quality: represents potential damage on biodiversity, focusing on species vulnerability and harmonizing previous recommendations related to land and water use, ecotoxicity, eutrophication, microplastics, acidification and climate change.
- Human health: represents potential damage on human population lifetime loss expressed in Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs), focusing on climate change, fine particulate matter impacts, toxicity, work environment impacts, lifestyle impacts including nutrition and physical activity, ionising radiation, and water scarcity.
- Socio-economic assets: evaluates the values of natural resources and ecosystem services from land use for human well-being.
- Normalization and weighting: applies a calculation framework to get a global normalization inventory and deterministic weights for all impact categories. It also ensures consistent LCI-LCIA linkage in collaboration with the global nomenclature system developed in GLAD to facilitate the implementation of the GLAM LCIA method in LCA software.

GLAM first provides characterization and weighting factors specific to each impact category, to compare scenarios within each category, as traditionally also done in midpoint-oriented methods. These impacts estimated at damage level can then be further compared and/or aggregated into total damages for each Area

of Protection. Weighting factors, retrieved through extensive surveys, then enable practitioners to compare impact scores across AoPs.

2.1.2 CALIMERO project

CALIMERO is a European Project funded by the European Union (with the number 101060546) whose goal is to create a common framework for the Life Cycle Assessment methodologies of certain bio-based industries' sectors (see link: [Calimero](#)). The CALIMERO project brings a consortium of 12 partners from 7 European countries, coordinated by Contactica S.L. (Spain). The consortium includes research institutions, industry leaders, and associations working together to improve environmental performance and sustainability across key sectors. Partners include CESEFOR (Spain), WELOOP, NEOVILI, and TECHTERA (France), the European Cellulose Insulation Association (Belgium), IVL, Essity, and BIM Kemi AB (Sweden), DTU (Denmark), LIST (Luxembourg), and EREKS garment (Turkey). CALIMERO aims to create a common framework for all bio-based industries to evolve in terms of sustainability by working with PEF indicators as well as with those proposed by CALIMERO. The presence of bio-based industries from five different sectors (construction, woodworking, textile, pulp & paper and biochemicals) in the consortium provides a valuable perspective of the industries' needs towards sustainability. Using the framework of the project, it is possible to reduce environmental impacts by identifying the main sources of pollutants and analyzing potential solutions, considering additionally economic and social dimensions. Finally, with more sustainable industries, Europe can become a greener and more resilient continent. Some specific objectives are:

- To identify the main barriers and incentives to apply life cycle thinking sustainability approaches and source of impacts in the target bio-based sectors.
- To define reference case studies and identify levers to improve life cycle sustainability assessment methodologies and sustainability performances.
- To improve existing sustainability assessment methodologies and their implementation for the 5 bio-sectors within the scope:
- LCIA methodology, will be improved, aligned with PEF through the consideration of regionalized impacts, circularity and criticality, temporal GHG emissions accounting, impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. This is the most relevant for our report.
- Integrate Life Cycle Costing (LCC) with Social-Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) considerations.
- To develop an MOO framework of industrial processes that integrates the improved LCSA methodologies based on PEF, for optimization of bio-based industrial processes with sustainability indicators.

2.1.3 ALIGNED project

ALIGNED is an European Project funded by the European Union Horizon Europe (grant agreement N° 101059430), with the goal of advancing the scientific field of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and collaborating with industries and representatives from five bio-based sectors: construction, woodworking, textile, pulp and paper, and bio-chemicals (See link: [ALIGNED](#)). ALIGNED is led by Aalborg University and formed by twelve partners from seven countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, Netherlands, Norway, Spain, Switzerland). Led by Aalborg University, the consortium is formed by Biomass Technology Group (BTG), Bloom Biorenewables, Centexbel, Foreco Dalfsen B.V., Kingspan Insulation BV, Institut National des Sciences Appliquées of Toulouse, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Oleon, Oleon NV, Sustainable Innovations, University of Antwerp, and Utexbel NV.

ALIGNED develops a modelling framework to perform high quality assessment studies across the bio-based sectors, with industrial relevance and interoperability.

The models and tools developed in ALIGNED will allow the performance of high-quality assessment studies across the bio-based sectors, with industrial relevance and interoperability. This is made possible by the iterative application and improvement of the new and harmonized models and tools in five specific cases of biobased industrial technologies (TRL 2-6), one for each sector.

The framework will be tested and improved via iterative application in five specific cases of biobased industrial technologies, one for each sector. The main objectives are:

- Improve, harmonize, and align LCA methodology for the assessment of bio-based industries.
- Demonstrate the power of the methodology to improve the environmental performance of five specific biobased technologies.
- Inform, involve, and empower all relevant stakeholders, enabling an efficient methodological uptake.

The following results will be delivered:

- Aligned and simplified methods to assess Environmental Performance (EP) that are used in the five industrial bio-based sectors on several key aspects that are relevant to all, namely land and biomass competition, carbon accounting, biodiversity, and uncertainty handling, and,
- Directly improve the EP in five exemplary industrial processes in said bio-based sectors, by disseminating the proposed solutions to key stakeholders in these sectors
- Disseminate data on EP - and recommendations to improve it - in the five industrial bio-based sectors in the EU.

2.1.4 ORIENTING project

ORIENTING is a Horizon 2020 project with the main objective to develop a robust and operational methodology for life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) of products towards a Circular Economy (See link: [ORIENTING](#)). The main purpose of ORIENTING to integrate a life cycle approach that includes the analysis of environmental, social and economic impacts. ORIENTING is composed by a consortium of 17 organizations based in 8 different countries around Europe. Participants cover the entire value chain of life cycle evaluations and provide a critical mass of expertise and excellence in key areas. The ORIENTING project is organized in 7 Work Packages (WP) with different goals to achieve:

- WP1. Framework and specifications. Lead by Ghent University: Starting-point that concerns the definition of a criteria-based scheme for the evaluation of existing methods and tools aligned with the UNEP/SETAC framework and the EU circular economy strategy.
- WP2. LCSA Methodology. Lead by VTT Technical Research Center of Finland Ltd: LCSA methodology development. It includes the progress beyond State-of-the-art for each sustainability domain.
- WP3. LCSA Operationalisation. Lead by TecNALIA: Operationalise methodological guidelines developed in WP2 by working on software and data and providing additional training materials for LCSA capacity building.
- WP4. Public demonstration. Lead by Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics: Implementation and test of the ORIENTING methodology in 5 different industrial environments (Ternua, Stora Enso, BASF, LEIBLEIN, Solana).
- WP5. Stakeholders' engagement and communication. Lead by EcoInnovazione: Specific engagement activities tailored to the different groups of stakeholders.
- WP6. Exploitation and dissemination of ORIENTING results. Lead by PRé Sustainability: Dissemination activities that will ensure that ORIENTING's outputs find their way to the concerned industrial and scientific communities, life cycle practitioners, company managers and academic researchers.

- WP 7. Project management and coordination. Lead by Tecalia: All tasks related to the overall project management.

2.2 Preselected methods for further evaluation

2.2.1 PEF method

The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2022) is an LCIA method to quantify the environmental impacts of products (goods or services) (Zampori et al., 2019). It builds on existing approaches and international standards. The overarching purpose of PEF information is to enable to reduce the environmental impacts of goods and services taking into account supply chain activities (from extraction of raw materials, through production and use and to final waste management). This purpose is achieved through the provision of detailed requirements for modelling the environmental impacts of the flows of material/energy and the emissions and waste streams associated with a product throughout its life cycle. The rules provided in the PEF method enable to conduct PEF studies that are more reproducible, comparable and verifiable, compared to existing alternative approaches. However, comparability is only possible if the results are based on the same Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs) (See link: [PEFCRs](#)). The development of PEFCRs complements and further specifies the requirements for PEF studies.

The Product Environmental Footprint project was initiated with the aim of developing a harmonized EU methodology for EF studies that can accommodate a broader suite of relevant environmental performance criteria using a life cycle approach. When adopted in 2013, the PEF method, whilst including more specific requirements than any alternative comparable existing method, it still included some generic requirements related to modelling certain activities (e.g. agriculture) and in particular related to the process of developing PEFCRs.

The currently available version of environmental Footprint (EF) method (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2023), which is the specific LCIA method in PEF, includes a total of 16 midpoint impact categories (**Table 1**), related to toxicity (freshwater ecotoxicity and human toxicity, carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects), climate change, pollution (ozone depletion, particulate matter, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation, acidification, eutrophication) and resources use (land, water, mineral and metals, and energy carriers). A single score is optional based on regional normalization and weighing.

Table 1. Description of EF impact categories for environmental sustainability evaluation.

LCA Assessment level	Impact category	D U e n s i c t r i p t i o n
Toxicity	Human toxicity, cancer	I C n T c U r h e 1 a s e d

		c a n c e r d i s e a s e s i n h u m a n p o p u l a t i o n
	Human toxicity, non-cancer	I n c r e a s e d n o n - c a n c e r c a s e s i n h u m a n

		p o p u l a t i o n
	Ecotoxicity, freshwater	P o t e n t i a l l y a f f e c t e d f r a c t i o n o f a q u a t i c s p e c i e s
Climate change	Climate change	R a d i a t i v e C O ₂ e q

		f o r c i n g o f G H G s o v e r 1 0 0 y e a r s
Pollution	Ozone depletion	D e s t r u c t i v e e f f e c t s o n t h e s t r a t o s p h e r i c o

		z o n e l a y e r o v e r 1 0 0 y e a r s
	Particulate matter	D i s s e a s e i n c i d e n c e s d u e t o p a r t i c u l a t e m a t t e r e m i

		s s i o n s	
	Ionizing radiation	H u m a n e x p o s u r e t o r a d i o a c t i v e m a t e r i a l	k B q U 2 3 5 e q
	Photochemical ozone formation	T r o p o s p h e r i c o z o n e c o n c e	k g N M V O C e q

		n t r a t i o n i n c r e a s e s d u e t o V O C s o x i d a t i o n
	Acidification	C r i t i c a l l o a d e x c e e d a n c e i n t e r

		r e s t r i a l e c o s y s t e m s d u e t o a c i d i f y i n g s u b s t a n c e s d e p o s i t i o n
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	C r i t i c a l

		o a d e x c e e d a n c e i n t e r r e s t r i a l e c o s y s t e m s d u e t o e u t r o p h y i n g s u b s t a n c e s
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		d e p o s i t i o n	
	Eutrophication, freshwater	I n c r e a s e o f p h o s p h o r o u s c o n c e n t r a t i o n i n w a t e r	k g P e q
	Eutrophication, marine	I n c r e a s e o f n	k g N e q

		i t r o g e n c o n c e n t r a t i o n i n w a t e r
Resources	Land use	D i m e n s i o n l e s s ³ a l i t y
	Water use	D e p r i v a t i o n - w e d e p r i

		t e d w a t e r c o n s u m p t i o n	v e d d w a t e r
	Resource use, minerals and metals	M i n e r a l a n d m e t a l s r e s o u r c e d e p l e t i o n b a s e d o n u s e	k g S b e q

		- t o - a v a i l a b i l i t y r a t i o
	Resource use, energy carriers	F M o J s s i l r e s o u r c e s d e p l e t i o n b a s e d o n l o w e r h e a t i

		n
		g
		v
		a
		l
		u
		e
		s

¹Comparative toxic unit for humans; ²Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems; ³Index reflecting land use impacts from four indicators provided by LANCA model.

2.2.2 ReCiPe 2016 method

The ReCiPe 2016 method is a widely used LCIA approach in environmental studies, designed to translate emissions and resource extractions into environmental impact scores (Huijbregts et al., 2017). ReCiPe 2016 is a midpoint and endpoint impact assessment method developed as a successor to the CML (midpoint) and Eco-indicator 99 (endpoint) methods. The name "ReCiPe" is derived from its two main contributors: RIVM, CML, and PRé Consultants.

It provides results at two levels: midpoints (**see Table 2**) and endpoints and three cultural perspectives (Individualist, Hierarchist, and Egalitarian), each reflecting different assumptions about time horizon and risk. Its flexible structure makes ReCiPe suitable for both detailed scientific analysis and high-level decision-making, and it is commonly implemented in LCA software such as SimaPro and OpenLCA.

Table 2. ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint Categories

Impact category	Description	Unit
Climate Change (Long-term & Short-term)	Measures greenhouse gas emissions contributing to global warming.	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone Depletion	Assesses emissions of substances that degrade the stratospheric ozone layer, increasing UV radiation exposure.	kg CFC-11 eq
Ionizing Radiation	Measures exposure to radioactive substances affecting human health.	kBq Co-60 eq
Photochemical Ozone Formation (Smog Formation)	Evaluates emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and NO _x that contribute to ground-level ozone and smog.	kg NMVOC eq
Fine Particulate Matter Formation	Quantifies emissions leading to formation of PM _{2.5} , affecting respiratory and cardiovascular health.	kg PM _{2.5} eq
Terrestrial Acidification	Caused by emissions like SO ₂ and NO _x that acidify soils, harming ecosystems.	kg SO ₂ eq
Freshwater Eutrophication	Assesses nutrient emissions (mainly phosphorus) causing algal blooms in freshwater bodies.	kg P eq
Marine Eutrophication	Evaluates nitrogen emissions that cause oxygen depletion and biodiversity loss in marine systems.	kg N eq
Terrestrial Ecotoxicity	Measures toxic impacts of chemical emissions on land-based organisms.	kg 1,4-DCB eq (1,4-dichlorobenzene).
Freshwater Ecotoxicity	Evaluates harmful effects of toxic substances on freshwater organisms.	kg 1,4-DCB eq
Marine Ecotoxicity	Assesses the impact of toxic substances on marine life.	kg 1,4-DCB eq.
Human Toxicity, Cancer Effects	Measures exposure to carcinogenic substances affecting human health.	kg 1,4-DCB eq
Human Toxicity, Non-Cancer Effects	Assesses the effects of toxic substances that cause non-cancer health outcomes.	kg 1,4-DCB eq
Land Use	Evaluates the impact of land occupation and transformation on biodiversity and ecosystem services.	m ² ·year.
Mineral Resource Scarcity	Quantifies the depletion of mineral resources based on economic effort to extract them.	kg Cu eq
Fossil Resource Scarcity	Assesses the use of fossil fuels and their availability over time.	kg oil eq
Water Consumption (Human)	Measures the potential health impact from lack of water availability.	m ³ water.

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Health)		
Water Consumption (Ecosystem Impact)	Evaluates water use that affects ecosystems (e.g., by reducing flow in rivers).	m ³ water.

2.2.3 LC-IMPACT method

The LC-IMPACT method provides internationally consistent and harmonized indicators for environmental impact categories (Verones et al., 2020). The method was developed through a collaborative effort involving 14 institutions across Europe, coordinated by Radboud University Nijmegen (The Netherlands). This initiative was part of the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) project titled '*Development and application of environmental Life Cycle Impact assessment Methods for improved sustainability Characterization of Technologies*' (See link: [FP7](#)). The main purposes are improving the robustness, transparency, and global applicability of LCIA and support policy making, product development, and comparative assessments. For this, LC-IMPACT aims to provide a "living" life cycle impact assessment methodology, which aims to be regularly updated to include the most important developments in LCIA, such as global coverage for the three main areas of protection (humans, ecosystems, resources), including spatially differentiated information where appropriate. Some other innovations include:

- Spatial resolution of CF according to the nature of impact (where possible) as well as spatially aggregated CF on country and global level, to facilitate coupling with LCI
- A new approach for assessing impacts to ecosystems, assessing global extinctions. This approach is more relevant and consistent than previous approaches, which mixed scales of extinctions.
- Explicit documentation of value judgments
- Explicit documentation of type of approach (marginal and/or average/linear)
- Quantitative uncertainty assessments for selected impact categories and qualitative discussion of uncertainties for all impact categories.

LC-IMPACT includes a total of 14 midpoint impact categories (**Table 3**) and three areas of protection (endpoint) (Human health, Ecosystem quality and Natural resources).

Table 3. LC-Impact Midpoint Categories

Impact category	Description	Unit
Climate Change	Measures the contribution of greenhouse gases to radiative forcing and global temperature rise.	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone Depletion	Evaluates the breakdown of the ozone layer caused by halogenated substances like CFCs and halons.	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate Matter Formation	Captures impacts on human health due to inhalable particles (e.g., from combustion processes).	kg PM _{2.5} eq
Terrestrial Acidification	Measures acidifying emissions (like SO ₂ , NO _x , NH ₃) that lead to soil acidification and damage to ecosystems.	kg SO ₂ eq
Freshwater Eutrophication	Measures nutrient enrichment in freshwater bodies due to phosphorus emissions, causing algal blooms and oxygen depletion.	kg P eq
Marine Eutrophication	Measures nutrient enrichment in freshwater bodies due to phosphorus emissions, causing algal blooms and oxygen depletion.	kg N eq
Terrestrial Eutrophication	Evaluates nitrogen deposition that disturbs terrestrial ecosystem nutrient balances.	kg N eq

Freshwater Ecotoxicity	Evaluates the potential harm of chemical emissions to freshwater aquatic ecosystems.	CTUe
Human Toxicity, Cancer Effects	Assesses long-term cancer effects on human health from chemical emissions through air, water, or soil.	CTUh
Human Toxicity, Non-Cancer Effects	Assesses the effects of toxic substances that cause non-cancer health outcomes.	CTUh
Land Use	Evaluates biodiversity loss due to land occupation and transformation (e.g., deforestation, agriculture).	Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) of species × area × time
Resource depletion, mineral and metals	Reflects the long-term scarcity and extraction impacts of natural resources.	kg Sb eq
Resource depletion, fossil	Reflects the long-term scarcity and extraction impacts of natural resources.	kg MJ eq
Water Use	Measures water consumption impacts based on regional water scarcity and competition.	m ³ water.

2.2.4 Ecological Scarcity method

The Ecological Scarcity Method is used to evaluate the environmental impacts associated with pollutant emissions and resource extraction identified through LCI analysis (Frischknecht et al., 2009) Central to this method are eco-factors, which represent the environmental burden of each unit of emission or resource use and are expressed in eco-points (See link: [Ecological Scarcity](#)).

Environmental impacts are quantified by applying these eco-factors, which are derived from environmental legislation or policy targets. The greater the extent to which current emissions or resource consumption exceed these environmental targets, the higher the resulting eco-factor—and consequently, the higher the eco-points assigned. Each eco-factor is calculated based on three key components, in line with ISO 14044 principles:

- **Characterisation** – Assesses the relative environmental harm of a substance (e.g., greenhouse gas, heavy metal) compared to a reference substance within a specific impact category (such as global warming, acidification, or radioactivity).
- **Normalisation** – Relates the quantity of emissions or resource use to the total annual environmental load within a reference region (typically Switzerland).
- **Weighting** – Compares the actual environmental load (current flow) with the allowable or target value (critical flow) as defined by policy. This reflects how far current conditions are from sustainable or legally acceptable levels.

The resulting eco-factors are then applied to the cumulative emissions and resource use data from the LCI, generating a total environmental impact score in eco-points. This method can support a wide range of applications, including: comparing products or processes, improving environmental performance, evaluating the total environmental impact of production facilities and assessing the environmental footprint of national consumption

2.2.5 IMPACT World+ method

IMPACT World+ was developed as a comprehensive update to three foundational LCIA methods: IMPACT 2002+ EDIP, and LUCAS (See link: [IMPACT World+](#)). It was created to meet the growing need for assessing regional environmental impacts associated with geo-referenced elementary flows. A key feature of IMPACT World+ is its provision of characterization factors (CFs) at four hierarchical levels of spatial resolution (Bulle et al., 2019).

- **Global default (non-spatially resolved)**

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- Continental
- Country-specific
- Native resolution (highest spatial granularity)

These levels enable more accurate assessment of regional impact indicators, incorporating associated uncertainty due to spatial variability. IMPACT World+ adopts a midpoint-to-damage assessment framework, offering a consistent and flexible structure through four complementary levels of interpretation:

- Midpoint level: Characterizes impacts at the problem level (e.g., climate change, acidification) (see **Table 4**).
- Damage level: Aggregates midpoint results into broader categories reflecting potential damage.
- AoPs damage level: Groups damage categories into three overarching AoPs: Human health, Ecosystem quality, and Resources & ecosystem services
- Areas of Concern (AoCs) damage level: Introduces an innovative structure that classifies damage categories into six sub-AoCs, based on thematic concerns, i.e., Water-related damages, Carbon-related damages, and other damages to human health and ecosystem quality

Table 4. Impact World+ Midpoint Categories

Impact category	Description	Unit
Climate change (short and long term)	Global warming potential from greenhouse gas emissions.	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone layer Depletion	Destruction of stratospheric ozone layer by substances like CFCs.	kg CFC-11 eq
Particulate Matter Formation	Emissions of PM and precursors affecting air quality and health.	kg PM _{2.5} eq
Photochemical Oxidant formation	Formation of ground-level ozone harmful to health and ecosystems.	kg NMVOC eq (non-methane volatile organic compounds)
Ionizing radiations – Human health	Exposure to ionizing radiation potentially damaging to human health.	kBq U235 eq
Terrestrial Acidification	Release of acidifying substances harmful to ecosystems.	Mol H ⁺ eq
Freshwater Acidification	Release of acidifying substances harmful to ecosystems.	Mol H ⁺ eq
Freshwater Eutrophication	Nutrient enrichment leading to oxygen depletion in freshwater bodies.	kg P eq
Marine Eutrophication	Nutrient enrichment in marine environments (mainly nitrogen).	kg N eq
Terrestrial Eutrophication	Nutrient deposition harmful to land ecosystems.	kg N eq
Freshwater Ecotoxicity	Toxic impacts on freshwater species from emissions.	CTUe
Human Toxicity, Cancer Effects	Assesses long-term cancer effects on human health from chemical emissions through air, water, or soil.	CTUh
Human Toxicity, Non-Cancer Effects	Assesses the effects of toxic substances that cause non-cancer health outcomes.	CTUh
Land transformation. biodiversity	Impacts of land transformation on biodiversity and soil.	PDF of species × area × time
Land occupation, biodiversity	Impacts of land occupation on biodiversity and soil.	
Mineral resource use	Depletion of mineral resources.	kg Cu eq

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Fossil Energy Use	Depletion of fossil energy carriers.	kg oil eq
Water scarcity	Use of freshwater in water-stressed regions.	m ³ world eq.

2.3 Supplementary Information: Set of conventional characterization factors or models

A set of CFs are organized in the **Supplementary Information Part 1**. This excel file is Part 1 of the supplementary Information of Task 2.3, where a set of CFs (Characterization factors) from different LCIA methods were collected, drawing on existing characterization models evaluated in prior EU-funded projects (previously discussed in Section 2).

Supplementary Information Part 1 is divided for each LCIA method according to the impact category evaluated into the following sections: Section 1 (S1): Human Toxicity; Section 2 (S2): Land Use; Section 3 (S3): Water Use; Section 4 (S4): Biodiversity; Section 5 (S5): Ecosystem Services.

3 HARMONIZATION THROUGH SELECTION, AGGREGATION AND/OR IMPROVEMENT OF LCIA METHODS

3.1 Procedure for classification of methods

The harmonization through selection of LCIA methods is performed through internal consultation (LCA4BIO project partners: LIST, INSA Toulouse and CONTACTICA) and review/evaluation of existing characterization methods. The LCIA method screening is based on the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) (European Commission, 2011), to develop a coherent and consistent analysis of existing characterisation models. The recommendations in this report are based on an analysis of a wide range of existing methods used in LCIA (as elaborated in section 2), which varies depending on the impact category evaluated, as detailed in the sections below for each category. Only the most recent and up to date version of the methods were considered. The purpose of this guidance document is to recommend default LCIA methods for each impact category, as the most suitable to be applied in BbS (Bio-based systems).

The LCIA methods were evaluated according to a set of criteria (outlined in section 3.2) and sub criteria (plus category-specific sub criteria, outlined in the excel file as supplementary information). The criteria consist of the fundamental requirements for LCIA methods, while the sub-criteria include complementary and specific characteristics of each individual impact category. Each sub criteria (also category-specific sub criteria) are scored on a qualitative scale (CS_{sub-c}):

- Full compliance (score: 2)
- Compliance in all essential aspects (score: 1)
- Compliance in some aspects (score: 0)
- Little compliance (score: -1)
- No compliance (score: -2)

In addition, each criteria and sub criteria were rated as either low (G) or high (H) importance for the impact category. High-importance criteria are those that significantly distinguish between models and affect key aspects of the characterization factors. While sub-criteria importance can vary by category, some are consistently rated high across all. In the case of H or G importance, they are rated with the score 1 and 2, respectively (I_{sub-c} in equation 1).

Thus, the total score ($Score_{i,j}$) assigned to the characterization LCIA methods is calculated through the equation 1, for category i , method j , including the importance of sub criteria (I_{sub-c} , defined as 1 for low importance and 2 in case of high importance) and the qualitative score CS_{sub-c} :

$$Score_{i,j} = \sum I_{sub-c} * CS_{sub-c} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

3.2 Calculation principles: application of criteria and sub criteria

To ensure that LCA studies are reliable, reproducible, and verifiable, it's essential to follow a set of fundamental analytical principles when applying LCIA methods. These principles serve as a foundation for the proper use of any LCIA method and help ensure that results are meaningful, consistent, and useful for decision-making.

Each criteria includes general and impact-specific sub-criteria. Below is a breakdown of the key criteria of the most used methods and its sub-criteria, while category-specific criteria are detailed in the supplementary information.

3.2.1 Completeness of scope

The LCIA method must comprehensively account for all relevant environmental inputs and outputs, including material and energy flows, emissions, and the use of natural resources. This means covering everything within

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the defined scope, based on the data requirements and selected impact assessment models. Ensuring completeness means that the method captures the full range of potential impacts within the characterization models, and data sources that together reflect the relevant environmental mechanisms. A complete LCIA method minimizes data gaps and methodological exclusions, thereby improving the reliability, transparency, and comparability of results across studies

Sub criteria example:

- Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments.
- Separate validity for Europe
- Temporal differentiation included

3.2.2 Environmental relevance

Environmental relevance refers to the degree to which the data, indicators, and models used accurately represent real-world environmental conditions and processes. All data collected and models applied should be directly relevant to the specific environmental context, ensuring that the assessment reflects the true nature of potential impacts. This means selecting datasets, characterization factors, and modeling approaches that correspond to the environmental mechanisms under investigation. Using scientifically robust and context-specific data enhances the credibility and applicability of the results, allowing for meaningful interpretation and informed decision-making. Environmental relevance ensures that LCIA outcomes are representative of the actual environmental consequences of the system being assessed.

Sub criteria example:

- Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality.

3.2.3 Scientific robustness

Each step in the LCIA process must strictly follow scientifically established procedures and methodologies. Maintaining internal consistency across data sources, models, and assumptions enables meaningful comparison between studies and supports the credibility of results. A scientifically robust LCIA method enhances confidence in its findings, particularly when used to inform environmental policy, corporate sustainability strategies, or decision-making processes. Ultimately, scientific robustness ensures that the conclusions drawn from the assessment are both defensible and reliable.

Sub criteria example:

- The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model, have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)
- The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation.

3.2.4 Certainty

Efforts should be made to identify, quantify, and minimize uncertainties in modelling and result reporting. This includes improving data quality and transparency about assumptions and limitations. Reducing uncertainty increases confidence in the outcomes and helps stakeholders make informed decisions.

Sub criteria example:

- Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms.

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3.2.5 Documentation, transparency and reproducibility

All aspects of the LCIA method and its application must be well-documented and transparent, allowing other users or stakeholders to understand, reproduce, and verify the results. Transparency is key for critical review, peer validation, and broader acceptance of the results. For this reason, data used needs to be documented in a way that analysis can be repeated by others.

Sub criteria example:

- The model documentation is published and accessible
- The set of CFs is published and accessible
- The characterization model is published and accessible
- Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and speciation differentiation.

3.2.6 Applicability

This principle refers to the practical usefulness and relevance of the method in real-world contexts, such as policy development, product design, or environmental reporting. An applicable LCIA method should generate results that are understandable, actionable, and directly supportive of decision-making processes. This means the method must be adaptable to different types of systems, sectors, and scales of analysis while remaining consistent with scientific and methodological standards.

Sub criteria example:

- The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools.

3.2.7 Acceptance

This likely refers to the recognition and adoption of the method by relevant stakeholders, including regulators, industry experts, and the scientific community. A method with broad acceptance is more likely to be used consistently and influence decisions.

Sub criteria example:

- The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable
- There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC
- The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts

A flowchart with the project and methods included are illustrated in **Figure 1**, also with the harmonization criteria considered and final method selected per category.

Figure 1. Procedure for classification of LCIA methods.

3.3 Toxicity selection criteria

LCIA Reviewer: Marjorie Morales (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology, LIST)

Human toxicity in LCA refers to the potential harm that chemical substances emitted during the life cycle of a product or process may cause to human health. This includes toxic effects from exposure to pollutants through inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact, over short or long periods. Human toxicity measures the potential impact of toxic substances released into air, water and soil. The cause-effect pathway accounts from the emission of the chemical to the environment, via fate and exposure, to affected human health. This pathway considers the environmental persistence (fate), accumulation in the human food chain (exposure) and toxicity (effect) of a chemical. Substances can come from various life cycle stages (e.g., raw material extraction, manufacturing, use, or disposal) and include heavy metals, organic compounds, pesticides and industrial chemicals. Human toxicity is often divided into two categories: cancer effects, defined as substance that can increase the risk of cancer: and non-cancer effects, including substances causing other chronic or acute health issues.

3.3.1 Method evaluation

Table 5 presents the evaluation sheet used to analyze the LCIA methods for toxicity category, including general criteria and sub-criteria. Category-specific sub-criteria are highlighted in blue. Sub-criteria marked with “H” indicate high importance, while those marked with “G” represent low importance.

Table 5. Qualitative scoring sheet outlining criteria, sub-criteria, and category-specific sub-criteria for the toxicity impact category.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance sub-criteria for Impact category (H-N)
Completeness of scope	Perform organic and inorganic chemicals (clearly differentiated)	H
	Differentiation of emission compartments	H
	Included cancer and non-cancer effects (clearly differentiated)	H
	Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments	G
	Separate validity for Europe	G

	Temporal differentiation included	H
Environmental relevance	Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality	H
	The model considers fate, exposure and effects in a quantitative way. Fate factors, intake fraction and dose-response information can be given as intermediary results	H
	Influential fate processes are taken into account as appropriate (e.g. –degradation, chemical reaction, volatilization, deposition, intermittent rain, direct deposition of pesticides on plants, colloid matter, sedimentation).	H
	Main impact pathways are covered as being relevant (inhalation, ingestion of meat, dairy products, fish, eggs, etc).	H
	Regarding dose-response, the Effect Dose 10% (ED10) or 50% (ED50) is used as a benchmark for the point of departure, avoiding safety factors. If not available extrapolation from NOAEL to LOAEL (No or Lowest Observable Adverse Effect Levels) is performed.	H
	Chemicals that test negative in cancer tests are differentiated from chemicals without available data.	H
Scientific robustness	The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)	H
	The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation	H
Certainty	Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms	G
Documentation, Transparency and reproducibility	The model documentation is published and accessible	H
	The set of CFs is published and accessible	H
	The characterization model is published and accessible	H
	Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and speciation differentiation	H
Applicability	The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools	H
Acceptance	The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable	G
	There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC	G
	The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts	G

3.3.2 LCIA methods evaluated

Some of the main challenges in human toxicity LCIA methods include the limited availability of public data on exposure, such as product use patterns and quantities of chemical ingredients, as well as gaps in the range of substances evaluated (both organic and inorganic), toxicity data (e.g., dose-response relationships), and the exposure routes considered. **Figure 2** illustrates the number of substances assessed, while **Table 6** summarizes the exposure routes included. Specifically, **Figure 2** displays the count of organic substances evaluated by each LCIA method, distinguishing between cancer effects (yellow bars) and non-cancer effects (blue bars). The PEF method considers the highest number of substances for non-cancer effects (3,319 substances), but the lowest number for cancer effects (1,023 substances). Moreover, in CALIMERO, novel CF were derived using machine learning methods (Ding et al., 2025). In contrast, the GLAM method does not differentiate between cancer and non-cancer effects, combining both within a single CF indicator. The number of emission compartments varies significantly across the evaluated LCIA methods (**Table 6**). For instance, the PEF method covers the greatest variety of air emission compartments, whereas the GLAM method includes the most compartments related to soil environments. The following section describes the scores obtained by each LCIA method based on different criteria and sub-criteria.

Table 6. Environmental compartments included in the different LCIA methods evaluated in toxicity

ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	USEtox 2.13	LC-IMPACT	GLAM Beta version	PEF 3.1
EMISSION TO WATER				
Freshwater	Cont. freshwater	Cont. freshwater	Freshwater	Freshwater
Marine water	Cont. sea water	Cont. sea water	Sea water	Sea water
			Water, unspecified	Water, unspecified
			WWTP	Water, unspecified (long-term)
EMISSION TO SOIL				
Agricultural soil	Cont. Agricultural soil	Cont. Agricultural soil	Agricultural soil	Agricultural soil
Industrial soil	Cont. Natural soil	Cont. Natural soil	Non-agricultural soil	Non-agricultural soil
			Soil, unspecified	Soil, unspecified
			SWT	
			Cont. freshwater sediment	
			Cont. sea sediment	
EMISSION TO AIR				
Urban air	Urban air	Urban air	Urban air close to ground	Urban air close to ground
Rural air	Cont. Rural air	Cont. Rural air	non-urban air close to ground	Urban air high stack
	Household, indoor air	Household, indoor air	household indoor air	Urban air low stack
	Industrial, indoor air	Industrial, indoor air	industrial indoor air	Urban air very high stack
			near-person air	Non-urban air close to ground
			air, unspecified	Non-urban air high stack
				Non-urban air low stack
				Non-urban air or from high stack
				Non-urban air very high stack
				Air, indoor
				Lower stratosphere and upper troposphere
				Air, unspecified
				Air, unspecified (long-term)

Figure 2. Number of substances for different LCIA methods, for toxicity cancer and no cancer effects at midpoint level.

3.3.2.1 ReCiPe 2016 v1.1

The toxicity assessment in ReCiPe 2016 includes separate midpoint factors for human cancer and non-cancer effects. The time horizon includes 20 and 100 years, while the exposure occurs via all intake routes (air, drinking water and food, see **Table 6**). The human toxicity potential is expressed in kg 1,4-dichlorobenzene-equivalents at the midpoint level and DALY at endpoint level. A total score of 62 is obtained for this method, obtaining the maximum score, in scientific robustness, certainty, transparency and acceptance. However, in the criteria completeness of scope, in the sub-criteria spatial differentiation beyond country is not covered in the method, as neither the separate validity for Europe. Similar in the criteria environmental relevance in the sub criteria, the model considers fate, exposure and effects in a quantitative way. Fate factors, intake fraction and dose-response information can be given as intermediary results', ReCiPe 2016 receive the minimum score, as it does not include this information as intermediary results.

3.3.2.2 GLAM V1.1

The human toxicity characterization factors in GLAM v1.1 are based on the USEtox model, focusing on inhalation and ingestion exposure related to the far-fields compartments (air, water and soil, **Table 6**) or a generic indoor compartment. GLAM only evaluated toxicity at midpoint level. The human toxicity potential is expressed in cases at the midpoint level. GLAM score the maximum punctuation in robustness, certainty, transparency, applicability and acceptance. However, lower score is obtained in the criteria of completeness of scope. Some limitations are related to spatiotemporal, migration from material surfaces to human skin, limited available data and models for toxicity dose-response as well as not including clearly differentiated organic and inorganic. In GLAM toxicity-related impacts on humans are described as a combination of cancer and non-cancer effects, each having a different severity and expressed as DALYs. Thus, GLAM obtains a score 46.

3.3.2.3 USEtox 2.13

Several characterization models for human toxicity indicators exist, all using mechanistic approaches that consider fate, exposure, and toxic effects. To unify their differing results in LCA, the USEtox™ consensus model was developed based on model comparisons, expert workshop recommendations, and the OMNIITOX project (Rosenbaum et al., 2008). These methods use multimedia, multi-pathway models to capture environmental

transfers and exposure routes comprehensively. The human toxicity potential is expressed in cases at the midpoint level and DALY at endpoint level. USEtox obtained a maximum score in all criteria, except in completeness scope, due to no inclusion of spatial and temporal differentiation, reaching a score of 64 over 80 points.

3.3.2.4 PEF v3.1

The PEF method scored 64, the same as USEtox. Both use USEtox® factors (v.2.1) for human toxicity impact categories (cancer and non-cancer). However, PEF offers several advantages over USEtox, mainly due to updated input data and calculation principles (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023). Specifically, (i) robustness factors were introduced to reduce the dominance of metals and address limitations in fate modeling for non-organic compounds; and (ii) high-quality data from EU agencies (European Chemicals Agency and European Food Safety Authority) ensure transparency and reliability. Additionally, PEF includes more specific environmental compartments compared to other methods (**Table 6**). The human toxicity potential is expressed in CTU_h at the midpoint level and DALY at endpoint level.

3.3.2.5 LC-IMPACT

A key strength of LC-IMPACT's human toxicity assessment is its spatial differentiation. Characterization factors are provided for various environmental compartments at multiple scales: local (indoor and urban air), continental and global (rural air, agricultural and natural soil, freshwater, and marine water). CFs are also available for 16 sub-continental zones (e.g., Central Asia, Central America & Caribbean) and 8 continental zones (e.g., North America, Latin America). LC-IMPACT evaluates toxicity impacts only at the endpoint level, expressed in DALYs for cancer and non-cancer effects. With a score of 48 out of 80, its main strengths lie in the criteria scientific robustness, certainty, transparency, applicability, and acceptance. However, limitations include incomplete scope and environmental relevance, as it does not clearly differentiate between organic and inorganic substances, lacks temporal differentiation, excludes intermediate results (e.g., fate factors, intake fractions), and does not define specific impact pathways (e.g., inhalation, ingestion of meat, etc.).

3.3.3 Recommended method for toxicity

Focusing on the final punctuation achieved in each method and previous discussion, the one selected as recommended for human toxicity impact assessment is the PEF method, with a score of 64 out of 80 points.

3.4 Land Use selection criteria

LCIA Reviewer: Eduardo Entrena Barbero (CONTACTICA)

Land use change (LUC) plays a pivotal role in enhancing bio-based production and consumption systems or initiatives, as many of these systems depend on raw materials extracted from forestry and agricultural sources. Depending on the type of use, this can be accounted for in terms of benefits in regard to carbon emissions sequestration or environmental burdens, such as biodiversity loss due to habitat fragmentation. Examples of this include soil degradation and erosion, or the disruption of the water cycle in a specific region or ecosystem (Bayer et al., 2023).

Consequently, land use extension requirements are emerging as a competing factor to consider, given their limited availability on a finite planet. However, there are other key factors to consider, including indirect land use change. In this regard, an initiative that reduces some residues and transforms them into potential value-added products could be promoted. However, the land extension requirements could result in a displacement of activities that are more essential, such as nutrition (e.g., food crop systems). In this regard, it is of utmost importance to consider not only the amount of land to be used, but also their potentialities, making a balanced

decision by considering the population needs (Daioglou et al., 2020).

3.4.1 Method evaluation

Table 7 presents the evaluation sheet used to analyze the LCIA methods for land use category, including general criteria and sub-criteria. Category-specific sub-criteria are highlighted in blue. Sub-criteria marked with “H” indicate high importance, while those marked with “G” represent low importance.

Table 7. Qualitative scoring sheet outlining criteria, sub-criteria, and category-specific sub-criteria for the land use impact category.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance sub-criteria for Impact category (H-N)
Completeness of scope	Activity name, reference product and location well defined	H
	Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments	H
	Separate validity for Europe	H
	Temporal differentiation included	G
Environmental relevance	Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality	H
	A specific underlying model is used	H
	Land transformation is well considered	H
	Land occupation is well considered	H
	Duration of physical changes is considered	G
Scientific robustness	Physical changes to soil are considered, e.g., altered soil functions, changes in water conditions or soil erosion	H
	The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)	H
Certainty	The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation	H
	Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms	G
Documentation, Transparency and reproducibility	The model documentation is published and accessible	H
	The set of CFs is published and accessible	H
	The characterization model is published and accessible	H
	Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and/or speciation differentiation	H
Applicability	The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools	H
Acceptance	The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable	G
	There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC	G
	The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts	G

3.4.2 LCIA methods evaluated

To appropriately assess land use, it is interesting to take a life cycle approach to account for potential environmental burdens while maintaining a holistic perspective of the activity to be developed. Then, nine different land use methods were selected and evaluated based on their strengths and weaknesses in accounting for Bbs.

3.4.2.1 ReCiPe 2016 v1.1

At midpoint level (i.e., problem-oriented perspective), land use is integrated in categories like terrestrial

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acidification or terrestrial ecotoxicity, apart from in three types of land occupations: (i) agricultural, (ii) urban and (iii) natural, measured in terms of area used over time (e.g., $m^2 \cdot a$ crop- eq). Conversely, at endpoint level (i.e., damage-oriented perspective), land use is perceived for its potential damage to ecosystem diversity, accounted for potential species loss in terms of Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) of species per area per year (i.e., $PDF \cdot m^2 \cdot year$) (Huijbregts et al., 2017). This method provides region-specific CFs that reflect species richness, land regeneration potential, and the duration and reversibility of impacts for different land use types. These factors translate the use of land into impact scores at both the midpoint and endpoint levels. These are available on the following link: [ReCiPe](#).

A total of 54 points are obtained for this method according to the scoring criteria proposed. On the positive side, there are some criteria like environmental relevance, scientific robustness or certainty. Likewise, other high-scored criteria are documentation, transparency and reproducibility, although in terms of third-parties availability it can be said that is limited, since it is directly managed by a core consortium. On the negative side, the indicator unit is not easy to understand or interpretate.

3.4.2.2 GLAM V1.0

Land use in GLAM is focused on ecosystem quality, particularly regarding biodiversity loss, ecosystem function alteration and species richness reduction. For measurement purposes, it uses species loss metrics over a specific area and time ($PDF \cdot m^2 \cdot year$) to capture the magnitude and severity of land use impacts on ecosystems. Included key aspects are the type (e.g., forests, grasslands, urban areas...) and nature (distinguishing between land occupation in terms of continuous use of land transformation in terms of conversion from one type to another) of land use, as well as the geographical context (variability depending on the region or ecosystem). The associated CFs can be found divided in two different volumes (See link: [GLAM v1 & v2](#)).

Only 1 point is obtained for the GLAM method. The criteria with the lowest score are the completeness of scope, since there is spatially explicit only at global scale, and the same applies for the no separate validity for Europe or the lack of inclusion of a temporal differentiation. However, other sub-criteria record the maximum punctuation, like the well consideration for both land occupation and transformation (in relation of the environmental relevance), while the rest usually record negative points, thus obtaining a very low score.

3.4.2.3 Ecological Footprint 2023

Developed by the Global Footprint Network, this method accounts for land use in terms of global hectares. This metric standardizes the productivity of various types of land (e.g., cropland, grazing land, and forest land) into a single unit. Additionally, it stands out for reflecting the occupation of aquatic systems, such as fishing grounds. Due to its scope of national or global resources, the method is more oriented toward policy-making actions since it provides an annual perspective on resource use, focusing on the balance between demand and the Earth's capacity (Van Den Bergh & Grazi, 2014).

The Ecological Footprint achieves 0 points for documentation, transparency and reproducibility, apart from acceptance the only two categories with more than two sub-criteria with the maximum score (i.e., 2 points). Therefore, the rest of them usually is scored with the lowest value (i.e., -2 points), standing out its low environmental relevance for the inclusion of a temporal differentiation or the duration of the physical changes.

3.4.2.4 PEF v3.1

The PEF method measures the impact of land use based on LANCA, a procedure focused on five soil-related indicators: (i) erosion resistance, (ii) mechanical filtration, (iii) physicochemical filtration, (iv) groundwater recharge, and (v) biotic production. Unlike the ReCiPe or GLAM methods, which focus on land use impacts from biodiversity terms, the PEF method scores soil quality and ecosystem functions based on deviation from

a reference state in dimensionless normalized units. Additionally, the European Commission recommends this method for providing a European spatial resolution (See link: [EPLCA](#)).

This method stands out among the rest of the methods from a negative perspective in the sense that it is developed in a closed environment under the European Commission, thus being unavailable by third parties (e.g., LCA experts) to refine it directly. Notwithstanding, for the rest of the criteria, most of them achieved positive punctuation, thus resulting in a final score of 51.

3.4.2.5 LC-IMPACT

The LC-IMPACT methodology provides a “living” life cycle impact assessment methodology, which aims to be regularly updated to include the most important developments in LCIA. In particular, LC-IMPACT aims to have global coverage for the three main areas of protection (humans, ecosystems, resources), including spatially differentiated information where appropriate in terms of global assessments and region-specific studies. Particularly, for the land use impact category, biodiversity loss and ecosystem service disruption are addressed (Verones et al., 2020).

57 points is the punctuation for the LC-IMPACT. This figure comes from its high spatial resolution, the appropriate way of covering both land occupation and transformations, as well as its market availability to specific LCA software tools (e.g., SimaPro or openLCA), among other aspects. Despite this, gaps emerge in terms of acceptance, since the indicator unit is not easily understood, apart from the principles of the model to interpret by non-LCIA experts.

3.4.2.6 Ecological Scarcity 2021

This method is based on the quantification of the environmental impact by comparing current emissions and resource use to predefined environmental targets. In the context of land use assessment, the method evaluated the impacts from land occupation and transformation in terms of biodiversity and ecosystem quality. In this sense, by incorporating eco-factors derived from environmental laws or political targets, Ecological Scarcity 2021 reflects the degree to which land use activities can exceed the environmental protection target established following a distance-to-target approach. Lastly, these eco-factors are then multiplied by the cumulative land use activities from the LCI, thus resulting in eco-points (Heijungs, 2023).

Despite the above, some sub-criteria stand out in this method, such as its availability in tailored LCA software, the relatively easy-to-understand eco-points (to be further communicated to a generic audience) or the availability of model by means of Swiss authorities. On the contrary, several key topics like environmental relevance, scientific robustness or certainty are negative scored. Therefore, this balance is translated in a total score of -15 points.

3.4.2.7 Ecosystem Damage Potential

The Ecosystem Damage Potential (EPD) method quantifies damage to ecosystems, particularly biodiversity loss and ecosystem service degradation resulting from land occupation and transformation. Consequently, CFs reflect some key variables such as ecosystem vulnerability or species richness, particularized by biogeographical region in units of PDF·m²·year.

In terms of the scoring procedure conducted, the EPD method achieves 24 points, standing out in criteria like environmental relevance or scientific robustness, including temporal differentiation, detailed cause-effect chains, apart from peer-reviewed models under related frameworks, while some others, such as documentation, transparency and reproducibility, applicability and acceptance, need further refinements.

3.4.2.8 IMPACT World+ v2.0.2 2023

IMPACT World+ is a globally regionalized method for LCIA, integrating multiple state-of-the-art developments as well as damages on water and carbon areas of concern within a consistent LCIA framework. Most of the regional impact categories have been spatially differentiated and all long-term impact categories have been subdivided into shorter-term damage (the first 100 years after the emission) and long-term damage categories. It is based on a midpoint-damage framework. Regarding the land use impact category, this is focused on the effects of both land occupation (e.g., m² of agricultural land occupied for crop production purposes in one year) and transformation (e.g., m² of forest land transformed to cropland) on ecosystem quality, biodiversity, and soil productivity, with regional specificity (Bulle et al., 2019).

49 points are recorded as total punctuation for this method. This value comes from the robustness of the modelling, the temporal dimension explicitly modelled or the active development and user feedback availability. In addition, negative points to this final punctuation are associated solely with the global scale addressed, the lack of inclusion of third-parties feedback in an easier way or the relatively hard to understand units that are used.

3.4.2.9 EPS v2020

The Environmental Priority Strategies (EPS) v2020 method is an LCIA method which assesses environmental impacts by translating emissions and resource use into a monetary value representing potential damage to human health, ecosystem quality, and resource availability. The land use impact category is assessed by considering the potential damage to ecosystem quality at national level resulting from land occupation and transformation. This includes the conversion of natural habitats into agricultural land, urban development, and other land-use changes, taking into consideration factors such as biodiversity loss, ecosystem functionality or soil quality degradation (Steen, 1999).

This method accounts for 60 points, since the minimum punctuation (i.e., 2 points) is only scored for its difficulty to understand for a general public audience without simplifying the complex eco-factor scoring system. On the other hand, a sub-criteria is recorded as null, due to data is limited to national or regional scales, while for the rest, in most of them, the maximum score is achieved.

3.4.3 Recommended method for land use impact

Focusing on the final punctuation achieved in each method, the one selected as recommended for land use impact assessment is EPS v2020, with a score of 60 out of 72 points. However, there are other promising methods with also achieve relatively good results, overpassing the threshold of 50 points, such PEF v3.1 (with 51 points) and LC-Impact (with 57 points).

3.5 Water Use selection criteria

LCIA Reviewer: Lucia Garcia Santos (CONTACTICA)

Assessing environmental impacts is essential, particularly when it comes to biobased systems and products. Due to its direct effects on resource depletion, ecosystem health, and human well-being, water use has become one of the most important environmental factors (Berger & Finkbeiner, 2010). However, evaluating the impacts of water use is complex and highly dependent on the impact assessment method employed.

The objective of this analysis is to evaluate and compare existing water use impact assessment methods to identify the most suitable ones for application in biobased systems and products. To ensure a consistent and transparent selection process, a structured evaluation method was applied. Each impact method was assessed against a set of predefined criteria, such as time dependency, regional sensitivity, comprehensiveness, Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

scientific robustness, and data availability. Based on their performance, methods were scored using a point-based system, allowing for an objective comparison.

This approach will support the identification of the most effective water use impact methods for bio-based systems, thus contributing to more accurate and meaningful environmental assessments.

3.5.1 Method evaluation

Table 8 presents the evaluation sheet used to analyze the LCIA methods for water use category, including general criteria and sub-criteria. Category-specific sub-criteria are highlighted in blue. Sub-criteria marked with “H” indicate high importance, while those marked with “G” represent low importance.

Table 8. Qualitative scoring sheet outlining criteria, sub-criteria, and category-specific sub-criteria for the water use impact category.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance sub-criteria for Impact category (H-N)
Completeness of scope	Activity name, reference product and location well defined	H
	Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments	H
	Separate validity for Europe	H
	Temporal differentiation included	H
Environmental relevance	Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality	H
	Size and stock/reserves considered	H
	Water consumption activity sector provided, e.g., agricultural, irrigation, etc.	H
	Duration of physical changes is considered	G
Scientific robustness	The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)	H
	The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation	H
Certainty	Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms	G
Documentation, Transparency and reproducibility	The model documentation is published and accessible	H
	The set of CFs is published and accessible	H
	The characterization model is published and accessible	H
	Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and/or speciation differentiation	H
Applicability	The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools	H
Acceptance	The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable	G
	There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC	G
	The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts	G

3.5.2 LCIA methods evaluated

Several water use impact assessment methods exist, each with its own assumptions, scope, and limitations, making method selection a critical task in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

Following the scoring process, the outcomes were examined in detail to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each method. This provided insights into the relative performance of the assessed methods and guided the selection of the most appropriate one for water use evaluations in biobased systems and products.

3.5.2.1 ReCiPe 2016 v1.1

ReCiPe 2016 v1.1 is a LCIA method that provides 18 midpoint (including water use) and 3 end point indicators, allowing a better understanding of environmental impacts (Huijbregts et al., 2017). Water use is assessed to evaluate how freshwater consumption affects the areas of protection human health and ecosystems, measuring how much water us consumed. At midpoint level, it converts water use into water scarcity as m³ H₂O eq.

While the impact method is available, supported by clear and peer-reviewed data, it received a total score of 17 points. This relatively low score is due to few key limitations of the method: notably, its lack of geographical and temporal differentiation, as well as its failure to account for the duration of physical changes. These factors are especially important when evaluating bio-based systems, where processes that change over time and specific regional variables play a huge role in determining environmental performance. The characterization factors are available here: [ReCiPe2016_CFs_v1.1_20180117 | RIVM](#).

3.5.2.2 GLAM V1.1

The GLAM v1.1 impact method was developed under the UNEP Life Cycle Initiative, looking for a harmonization of LCIA, including both midpoint and endpoint indicators for water use. For water use impact, the method relies on the data generated in the AWARE method, also part of this study and evaluation (Frischknecht & Jolliet, 2019). In that sense, the performance of the impact method as part of the GLAM method was evaluated.

The method focuses not just on water consumption, but also on water scarcity impacts. Moreover, it includes regionalized characterization factors by country, capturing spatial variability in water availability and demand, relying on the AWARE impact method. However, it does not differentiate water use across economic sectors, nor the origin of water reserves are considered. For that reasons, GLAM v1.1 scored a total of 13 points in the comparative evaluation.

The characterization factors are provided in m³ deprived, quantifying how much water use contributes to local water scarcity, available here: <http://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/applying-lca/lcia-cf>

3.5.2.3 AWARE v1.2

The AWARE (Available WATER REmaining) method evaluates water use impacts, with a focus on water scarcity. It is a recognized method, and it is used as part of the GLAM framework, being also included in the PEF v3.1 impact method. The AWARE method uses the indicator water scarcity at midpoint level (Boulay et al., 2018).

The method distinguishes impacts at country or watershed scale, allowing impacts to be calculated based on a geographic context. Even though the temporal scope is based on long-term hydrological averages and it does not distinguish between water uses per sector, it reflects actual water stress conditions, enables comparison between regions and the data is transparent, available and peer/reviewed. The method is well explained and easy to understand, with analysis of uncertainty and limitations of the method. For that reason, it scored a total of 43 points.

The characterization factors are provided in m³ deprived, quantifying how much water is left in a region after demands are met, available here: <http://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/applying-lca/lcia-cf>

3.5.2.4 PEF v3.1

The PEF (Product Environmental Footprint) v3.1 impact assessment method for water use was not separately included in the evaluation. This is because the water scarcity impact category in PEF v3.1 relies directly on the characterization factors developed by the AWARE method. Since AWARE was already evaluated independently as part of this study, assessing PEF v3.1 separately would not provide additional insights of its water use impact assessment approach. Therefore, to avoid redundancy and maintain methodological clarity, only the original

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AWARE method was considered in the scoring analysis.

3.5.2.5 LC-IMPACT

The LC-IMPACT method was developed as joint effort between recognized researchers, and focuses on regionalizing the damage level for 7 of 11 impacts categories for a clear spatial differentiation, particularly relevant in categories such as water use (Verones et al., 2020).

The method scored 34 points, assuring the robustness of the method. Like the AWARE method, water use impact is also measured as m³ deprived and the characterization factors are region-specific. The method is easy to understand and can be applied in most of the widely used LCA software tools. Yet, it lacks temporal differentiation and further developments and refinements, such as data availability, must be done. The characterization factors can be downloaded in excel file here: [Life cycle impact assessment methodology](#)

3.5.2.6 CML v4.8

CML is an LCIA method developed by the Institute of environmental Sciences from Leiden University in the Netherlands. It is midpoint-oriented only and is available in most of the LCA software tools (See link: [CML](#))

CML v4.8 is a transparent, freely available and easy to interpret impact method. However, it lacks regionalized impact modelling or endpoint results in categories such as water use. The method does not differentiate water consumption per sector and the duration of physical changes are also not considered. Due to these limitations, it is less suitable for sustainability assessments in bio-based systems and scored a total of 16 points. The characterization factors can be downloaded from the website of Leiden University here: [CML-IA Characterisation Factors - Leiden University](#)

3.5.2.7 Ecological Scarcity 2021

The Ecological Scarcity 2021 method quantifies environmental impacts by comparing environmental loads to defined Swiss environmental thresholds defined by legislation, published by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN, 2021).

The method measures impact in eco-points (UBP) per unity of quantity, allowing a better interpretation and comparison of impacts among products. However, the method's limited regionalization, lack of endpoint modeling, and absence of sector-specific differentiation, reduce its effectiveness in evaluating complex or global systems, such as bio-based supply chains or water use in site-specific contexts. Despite these limitations, the method is regularly updated and remains highly adaptable, with strong potential for further development and broader application of the eco-points system across additional regions due to its relevance to current environmental policies and legislations. For that reason, the method scored a total of 27 points. The characterization factors can be downloaded here: [Swiss Eco-Factors 2021 according to the Ecological Scarcity Method](#)

3.5.2.8 EPS v2020

The EPS (Environmental Priority Strategies in product design) v2020 is a LCIA that quantifies environmental impacts estimating damage in monetary terms such as Euro (Steen & Rydberg, 2020).

The EPS 2020 method quantifies environmental impacts by translating potential damage into monetary values, aligning well with cost-benefit frameworks and supporting decision-making from an economic perspective. However, it lacks both geographical and temporal differentiation, limiting its ability to assess location-specific impacts such as water scarcity. Additionally, the method does not distinguish between different sectors of

water use, reducing its suitability for sector-specific assessments, which are critical for evaluating the sustainability of bio-based systems. On that ground, the method scored a total of 9 points. Characterization factors are available in pdf file format here: [Microsoft Word - EPS 2020d weighting factors part 1.1\).](#)

3.5.2.9 IMPACT World+ v2.0.2 2019

IMPACT World + v2.0.2 2019 is an LCIA method that assess impacts through 24 midpoint indicators, 46 damage indicators and 2 areas of protection. Some indicators have temporal or regional differentiation (Bulle et al., 2019). The method has an improved cause-effect modelling and offers regionalised differentiation by country, continent, and watershed for some categories. However, no temporal differentiation is included in the midpoint indicator water scarcity, requires a detailed inventory and its limitations in the assessment in water use, made it score a total of 2 points. It is available in SimaPro, openLCA, and other LCA software tools, and the characterisation factors can be downloaded here: <https://www.impactworldplus.org/download/>

3.5.3 Recommended method for water use

AWARE v1.2 was chosen as the recommended impact method to assess water use. This is due to its potential to evaluate not just how much water is used, but how much water remains after needs are met in a specific region, being critical for bio-based systems, where production is location-dependent and water use is of importance in vulnerable and marginal areas. Moreover, it helps identify where water use is unsustainable and how stressed that region is, allowing policymakers to adapt water use strategies.

3.6 Biodiversity selection criteria

LCIA Reviewers: Omar Bayomie and Ligia Tiruta-Barna (INSA Toulouse)

3.6.1 Method evaluation

Table 9 presents the evaluation sheet used to analyze the LCIA methods for biodiversity category, including general criteria and sub-criteria. Category-specific sub-criteria are highlighted in blue. Sub-criteria marked with “H” indicate high importance, while those marked with “G” represent low importance.

Table 9. Qualitative scoring sheet outlining criteria, sub-criteria, and category-specific sub-criteria for the biodiversity impact category.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance sub-criteria for Impact category (H-N)
Completeness of scope	Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments	H
	Separate validity for Europe	H
	Temporal differentiation included? (different future climate scenarios considered, i.e., RCP)	G
Environmental relevance	Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality	H
	The model considers gradients across species and regions?	G
	Among the Ecosystems, Terrestrial, freshwater and Marine ecosystems are included?	H
	Among the main taxonomic groups, mammals, birds and amphibians are included?	H
	Among the main pressures on biodiversity, land use and water use are included in the model?	H
Scientific robustness	The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)	H
	The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation	H
Certainty	Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms	G
	The model documentation is published and accessible	H

Documentation, Transparency and reproducibility	The set of CFs is published and accessible	H
	The characterization model is published and accessible	H
	Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and speciation differentiation	H
Applicability	The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools	G
Acceptance	The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable	G
	There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC	H
	The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts	G

3.6.2 LCIA methods evaluated

3.6.2.1 ReCiPe 2016 v1.1

ReCiPe 2016 method is the result of ancient versions with improvements from an exhaustive analysis of the existent LCIA methods. The method provides a harmonized implementation of cause-effect chains to calculate the midpoint and endpoint impacts. Endpoint impacts are classified in 3 area of protection: human health (DALY), ecosystem quality (species*year) and resources (US dollar), commonly used with “points” unit (after aggregation, normalization and weighting). The combination of the midpoint impacts within common damage pathways and finally in the area of protection are represented in the **Figure 3**.

The advantage of ReCiPe over the other methods is that the damage on ecosystems includes different stressors, from land use to ecotoxicity, climate change, etc. without the threat of double counting, if the method is applied in its integrity (to estimate all impact categories). There is no temporal differentiation, but in light of its evolution, we qualify ReCiPe2016 as a mature method (with a score 45 over a maximum of 62). The method provides CFs at global scale and at country and continental scales, available here: <https://www.rivm.nl/en/life-cycle-assessment-lca/downloads> .

Figure 3. Impact categories in ReCiPe2016 and their combination into areas of protection. From Huijbregts et al. (2018).

3.6.2.2 GLAM V1.1

GLAM method includes biodiversity impact at endpoint, from the land use and land use change mid-point impacts. The method is based on a cause-effect scheme and modelling approach, which is summarized in the **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Model used to calculate the biodiversity indicators in GLAM v1.1. From UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2016

Two indicators can be calculated: regional and global potential species loss. Five taxonomies are included: mammals, reptiles, birds, amphibians and vascular plants. Six major land use types (annual crops, permanent crops, pasture, urban, extensive forestry, and intensive forestry) are included allowing the connection with the LCI. The method lacks a temporal dimension.

The characterization factors are provided in global PDF/m² (for occupation) and global PDF × year/m² (for transformation), available here: <http://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/applying-lca/lcia-cf>

The consensus is not still reached, and for this reason, the recommendation is to not use the method for comparisons or product labelling, but only for hotspot analysis in LCA. Moreover, an additional advise is to not use the method at country average level but only for the foreground system (local).

This method evaluates biodiversity loss from land use/transformation only, and its use should be verified for double counting with ecotoxicity impacts. The method is not yet mature, obtaining a score 30, because of lack of extensive application to different case studies which is a necessary step for a fair validation.

3.6.2.3 LC-IMPACT

This method gathers knowledge and concepts from other LCIA methods into a more complete methodology (Verones et al., 2020). It is the result of a compilation, analysis and refinement of the existent LCIA methods, in the framework of the LC-IMPACT FP7 project. It provides CFs for 11 impact categories at endpoint grouped in 3 main area of protection. The damage on biodiversity is expressed as global species extinction equivalents, based on PDF (potential disappeared fraction), i.e. the PDF value of the studied system is related to the global pool of species (thus the result is a fraction, dimensionless). Moreover, 3 types of ecosystems are considered separately in the area of protection “ecosystem quality”: terrestrial, fresh water and marine. The **Figure 5** shows the cause-damage effect pathways considered in LC-IMPACT.

Figure 5. Impact categories and area of protection in LC-IMPACT method. From Verones et al. (2020).

This method offers variants for CFs depending on the following parameters:

- Spatial detail (for those impact categories where spatialization is relevant): the “native” spatial level, country averages, continental averages and a global average. For example, the native resolution for land stress is ecoregions with similar ecological conditions.
- Linear/average or marginal CFs: marginal approach is recommended for small emissions which don’t modify the background level, while average is recommended when applied to large flows of environmental interventions.
- The units for ecosystem quality impact score: PDF*year. The global PDF is an indicator for the risk of irreversible extinction of species, while the regional one the risk of ecosystem misfunctioning.
- Certainty perspective: 4 variants of CFs are proposed, depending on the time horizon and the level of current evidence of the impact (current state of knowledge). 100 years is the shortest time horizon. Two models address all impacts/factors in the cause-damage pathway (one at 100y, another at very long term), and two others include only certain pathways for the 2 time horizons.

LC-IMPACT is a mature and complete LCIA method (obtaining a score of 50 points) and can be recommended for biodiversity damage. The CFs of LC-IMPACT v1.3 are available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/6200606>

3.6.3 Recommended method for Biodiversity impact

Currently, only the ReCiPe2016 method is available with the existent LCA software. ReCiPe endpoint is a mature method and can be used for biodiversity impact assessment by the LCA practitioners. LC-IMPACT method offers more sophisticated approaches but the method is not yet implemented with LCA common software and needs more expertise to be correctly used. It can be used by researchers or advanced LCA practitioners.

3.7 Ecosystem services selection criteria

LCIA Reviewer: Tianran Ding (LIST)

3.7.1 Method evaluation

Table 10 presents the evaluation sheet used to analyze the LCIA methods for Ecosystem services in LCA, Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

including general criteria and sub-criteria. Category-specific sub-criteria are highlighted in blue. Sub-criteria marked with “H” indicate high importance, while those marked with “G” represent low importance.

Table 10. Qualitative scoring sheet outlining criteria, sub-criteria, and category-specific sub-criteria for the ES.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance sub-criteria for Impact category (H-N)
Completeness of scope	Activity name, reference product and location well defined	H
	Spatial differentiation beyond country, continental and world compartments	H
	Separate validity for Europe	H
	Temporal differentiation included	G
Environmental relevance	Mechanism describing the cause-effect chains are included with acceptable quality	H
	A specific underlying model is used	H
	Land transformation is well considered	H
	Land occupation is well considered	H
	Duration of physical changes is considered	G
	Physical changes to soil are considered, e.g., altered soil functions, changes in water conditions or soil erosion	H
Scientific robustness	The critical part of the model including the parameters used in the model have been peer reviewed (journal, panel, book, etc.)	H
	The model including the underlying data have a good potential for being consistently improved and further development, e.g., geographical/ emission and temporal differentiation	H
Certainty	Uncertainty estimates of the indicators are provided, motivated and reported in statistical terms	G
Documentation, Transparency and reproducibility	The model documentation is published and accessible	H
	The set of CFs is published and accessible	H
	The characterization model is published and accessible	H
	Ability for third parties to freely generate additional, consistent factors and to further develop model, e.g., incorporating further geographical, temporal and/or speciation differentiation	H
Applicability	The method is straightforward to apply in most market-relevant LCA software tools	H
Acceptance	The indicator unit is easily understood and interpretable	G
	There is an authoritative body behind the general model principles, e.g., IPCC	G
	The principles of the model are easily understood by non-LCIA experts	G

3.7.2 LCIA methods evaluated

3.7.2.1 LANCA project

Most current approaches for integrating ecosystem services (ES) into Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) involve linking inventory flows—such as land occupation and land transformation—to ES impacts, treated as new midpoint impact categories. Various studies have proposed methodologies and developed region-specific characterization factors (CFs) to assess the effects of land use and land use change on ES, including biotic production, climate regulation, freshwater regulation, erosion control, and water purification, for integration into existing LCA frameworks (Hardaker et al., 2022). These other methods were not evaluated as they are not operationally available for any LCI database and software.

The LANCA® (Land Use Indicator Value Calculation) project, developed by Fraunhofer IBP, provides a robust, spatially explicit method to integrate land use impacts into Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Beck & Fraunhofer-

Institut für Bauphysik, 2010). It calculates characterization factors (CFs) for both land occupation (ongoing use) and land transformation (change in use) impacts on soil quality. The LANCA® project offers a scientifically robust, spatially aware, and policy-integrated method for calculating indicators for soil functions (e.g. erosion and water regulation, filtration capacity) originally based on site-specific data. LANCA developers have also recently developed CFs directly associated with land use. LANCA includes spatial resolution, which can be site-specific (e.g., country), including permanent and reversible land transformation, as well as land occupation indicators, and is widely used and recommended (available in GABI LCA software), some of the weaknesses of the method is the no inclusion of temporal differentiation or incertitude. The total score obtained is 64 (of a maximum score of 72).

3.7.3 Recommended method for ES

The only method evaluated on integrating ES in LCA is the LANCA model based on the recommendation of CALIMERO project (more details in Deliverable D1.3: ‘Characterization of the main methodological gaps in sustainability assessment of bio-based sectors’). This is proposed as the most robust method for integrating indicators for soil functions (ES), with a score of 64 over a maximum of 72 points.

3.8 Summary of harmonization of LCIA methods for BbS

The results of the analysis of the shortlisted LCIA methods are shown in summarized form in **Figure 6** for each of the impact categories (method selected highlighted in red square). See **Table 11** for score values.

The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analyses for the selected method, addressing Human Toxicity, Biodiversity, Land Use, Water Use, and Ecosystem Services, are detailed in **Tables 12 through 16**.

Table 11. Summary of total score obtained for different LCIA methods in the categories: land use, water use, human toxicity, biodiversity and ES.

Land use →	Max. score	Ecological Footprint 2023	Ecological Scarcity 2021	Ecosystem Damage Potential	Impact World+ v2.0.2 2023	PEF v3.1	EPS v2020	LC-Impact	ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	GLAM v1.0
Score →	72	0	-15	24	49	51	60	57	54	1
Water Use →	Max. score	GLAM v1.0	AWARE v1.2	PEF v3.1	CML v4.8	Ecological Scarcity 2021	EPS v2020	Impact World+ v2.0.1 2019	ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	LC-Impact
Score →	66	13	43	43	16	27	9	2	17	34
Toxicity →	Max. score	ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	GLAM v1.0	USEtox 2.13	PEF v3.1	LC-Impact				
Score →	80	62	46	64	64	48				
Biodiversity →	Max. score	GLAM v1.0	ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	LC-Impact						
Score →	62	30	45	50						
Ecosystem Services →	Max. score	LANCA v2.5								
Score →	72	64								

Figure 6. Normalized score values (to the maximum score, see Table 11 for scores) for the LCIA methods in different impact categories.

Table 12. SWOT analysis for the LCIA method selected for Human toxicity category: PEF v3.1

Human Toxicity LCIA Method selected: PEF v3.1 (Product Environmental Footprint)	
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PEF adopts USEtox, a globally recognized model, ensuring consistency with the best available science. Update calculations principles, i.e., robustness factors were introduced to reduce dominance of metals and in fate modelling for non-organic compounds. Transparency and reproducibility: Characterization factors and assumptions are published and standardized, facilitating reproducibility across studies. High-quality data from EU agencies ensure transparency and reliability. PEF includes more specific environmental compartments compared to other methods. PEF Aligns with EU goals for safe and sustainable chemicals, circular economy, and green product design.
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data intensity, PEF toxicity models require large, detailed life cycle data sets. Results are only as good as the data and assumptions behind them. High uncertainty and data gaps, toxicity models rely on limited or estimated data for many substances; missing physicochemical and fate data reduce accuracy. USEtox provides generic continental- and global-scale exposure models, which often neglect local or workplace exposure. Thousands of substances in commerce are not yet characterized, especially transformation products or complex mixtures. Models do not fully capture bioaccumulation, mixture effects, or non-linear dose-response relationships. Toxicity indicators (CTUh) are difficult to interpret for non-experts, limiting their usefulness.
Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future integration of regionalized USEtox and dynamic models. Harmonizing PEF data with regulatory databases, such as REACH, CLP could enhance data quality and policy relevance. Improved data availability through digitalization: Digital product passports and supply-chain transparency initiatives can provide better emission and chemical-use data. Toxicity indicators can guide eco-design and chemical substitution efforts, supporting safer design and substitution.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High uncertainty in toxicity results may undermine confidence and be perceived as lack of reliability. Limited access to substance-specific emission data due to data confidentiality or data gaps can hinder accurate assessments. Differences between PEF (impact-based) and regulatory frameworks (risk-based) could cause confusion or misuse of results.

Table 13. SWOT analysis for the LCIA method selected for Biodiversity category: ReCiPe 2016.

Biodiversity LCIA Method selected: ReCiPe 2016 v1.1	
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrates multiple midpoint categories (acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, land use, water use, etc.) into a single, coherent endpoint expressing biodiversity loss. The method includes different stressors, reflecting real ecological processes. Aligned with ISO 14040/44 standards and widely implemented in major LCA tools (SimaPro, openLCA). Incorporates regionalized impact pathways where possible, the method provides characterization factors at global scale and at country and continental scales, improving representativeness. Provides a single, interpretable metric (species-year) that helps communicate ecosystem impacts.
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endpoint modeling requires multiple assumptions and conversions from midpoints to species loss, representing uncertainty in the results. Limited ability to reflect local biodiversity conditions, habitat types, or regional conditions, reflect an incomplete spatial resolution. Limited validation of species-pressure relationships, especially for ecotoxicity and land-use pathways. Many complex processes (e.g., species interactions, ecosystem resilience, thresholds) are oversimplified or omitted.
Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of regional and habitat-specific models could include region-specific biodiversity response.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved spatial data and remote sensing could greatly refine spatial modeling. Expansion from species loss to functional biodiversity and ecosystem service loss, could improving decision-making relevance.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A single model could limit scientific innovation and discourage alternative biodiversity models. Rapid progress in biodiversity modeling (e.g., IPBES, PREDICTS) could render current impact pathways outdated without regular updates.

Table 14. SWOT analysis for the LCIA method selected for Land use category: EPS v2020.

Land Use	LCIA Method selected: EPS v2020 (Environmental Priority Strategies)
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EPS goes beyond species loss to include impacts on ecosystem quality, human health, carbon storage, and resource availability, aligning with the ecosystem services framework. Land use impacts are linked with climate change, biodiversity, and resource depletion through a unified valuation model. Translates land use impacts into economic terms enabling direct integration with cost-benefit analyses. Expressing land use damage in monetary terms makes it more tangible for non-LCA experts.
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Models may not fully capture non-linear ecosystem responses or regional ecological differences. Monetary conversion of ecological loss involves subjective assumptions. Monetary values can obscure underlying ecological mechanisms, making interpretation of results less intuitive. Data availability for global or regional land use inventories and ecosystem service valuation data are still limited.
Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with spatially explicit biodiversity models could improve spatial realism and regional relevance. Monetary valuation facilitates integration into corporate sustainability accounting and product eco-design. Synergies with ecosystem service research. Advances in digital data, such as remote sensing and AI-based land monitoring could provide more precise and dynamic land occupation data.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EPS's economic valuation framework differs from physical-based methods (e.g., ReCiPe, PEF), limiting comparability. EPS is less widely implemented in mainstream LCA software compared for example to ReCiPe or PEF. Results are sensitive and depend on socio-economics assumptions, which may vary by country or context. Aggregating ecological impacts into a single monetary value (oversimplification) could obscure specific land-use trade-offs or misguide land management decisions.

Table 15. SWOT analysis for the LCIA method selected for Water Use category: AWARE v1.2

Water Use	LCIA Method selected: AWARE v1.2 (Available Water Remaining)
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed through international collaboration (UNEP-SETAC, GLAM project) and adopted in Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 and ISO 14046 frameworks. The method distinguishes between impacts at country or watershed scale, allowing Spatial differentiation (regionalized). Considers environmental flow requirements and human water consumption, integrating ecological and socio-economic dimensions. Uses a clear, single indicator (AWARE score) making it intuitive for practitioners. Integrated into major software (SimaPro, openLCA, Brightway, GaBi).
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses long-term hydrological averages, annual average data being limited in temporal resolution, which masks seasonal water scarcity. Focuses on water quantity, ignoring water quality, e.g., pollution or contamination. Global hydrological models and datasets can misrepresent conditions in regions with limited data, lacking local accuracy. Does not distinguish between water uses per sector. AWARE measures <i>potential deprivation</i> rather than concrete environmental damage, e.g., human health impacts or ecosystem quality.
Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with dynamic and local models and/or remote-sensing data could capture temporal variability. Combination with water pollution, eutrophication, or ecological status would provide a more holistic assessment. Could guide future regional water management and sustainable product design at policymaking level. Sector-specific characterization factors for, e.g., agriculture, textiles can improve applicability and decision support.

Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data uncertainty and modeling biases (differences in hydrological models and assumptions) can lead to inconsistent results. ▪ Requires frequent updates and recalibration, changes in precipitation and runoff patterns could invalidate static characterization factors. ▪ AWARE remains primarily a technical tool; translation into actionable water management policies is still limited.
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Table 16. SWOT analysis for the LCIA method selected for Ecosystem services: LANCA

ES LCIA Method selected: LANCA (Land Use Indicator Value Calculation)	
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Calculates multiple indicators for soil functions (e.g., erosion resistance, water filtration), capturing the multifunctionality of land. ▪ The method is scientific robust, based on biophysical soil and ecosystem processes, providing a mechanistic understanding of land use impacts. ▪ Differentiates between temporary occupation and reversible or permanent transformation, improving life cycle realism. ▪ Allows for spatial resolution using site-specific soil, climate, and land cover data. ▪ Each function is modelled separately, enabling adaptations for specific applications or regions.
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Requires detailed input data (data intensive) on soil properties, land cover, climate, management practices, etc. ▪ The method is more complex and computational demanding than typical LCA midpoint methods, limiting its use. ▪ Limited global coverage: Initially developed and validated mainly for European conditions; transferability to tropical or arid regions may reduce accuracy. ▪ Lack of direct linkage to biodiversity. ▪ Lack of temporal differentiation or uncertainty. ▪ Limited integration in mainstream LCA software, it is available in GABI LCA software.
Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LANCA's regional precision is becoming increasingly valuable, because of growing demand for regionalized and land-quality-based LCA methods. ▪ Integration with GIS and remote sensing data could automate and scale assessments. ▪ Combining LANCA with models like ReCiPe biodiversity endpoints can provide a holistic picture of land use impacts.
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Competition with other land use impact methods more simplified and widely adopted, such as ReCiPe, LC-Impact, PEF. ▪ Data inconsistency across regions (global soil and land cover data) can lead to inconsistencies when comparing results across case studies. ▪ Some technical indicators like “groundwater recharge potential” or “mechanical filtration capacity” may be difficult to communicate to non-specialists. ▪ Static input parameters may not fully capture evolving soil and ecosystem conditions under Climate change and land degradation dynamics.

3.9 Supplementary Information: Harmonization of LCIA methods

The harmonization method is detailed in **Supplementary Information Part 2**. The harmonization method, based on a multi-criteria scoring approach, evaluates each LCIA method according to seven key criteria: completeness of scope, scientific robustness, relevance to bio-based systems, certainty, transparency, applicability, and level of acceptance.

Supplementary Information Part 2 describes the selection methodology and criteria and sub criteria for each impact category and is organized for each LCIA method according to the impact category evaluated: Section 1 (S1): Human Toxicity; Section 2 (S2): Land Use; Section 3 (S3): Water Use; Section 4 (S4): Biodiversity; Section 5 (S5): Ecosystem Services.

4 IMPROVED TEMPORALLY DIFFERENTIATED CHARACTERIZATION IMPACT MODELLING

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4.1 Temporal considerations in life cycle impact assessment methods

Dynamic Life Cycle Assessment (DLCA) is an extension of conventional LCA that incorporates temporally induced changes affecting both the results and interpretation of the modelled system. In contrast, Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA) evaluates a system at a specific point in the future, considering future aspects & conditions, which may or may not include temporal differentiation across all assessment phases. A full dynamic LCA integrates temporal changes throughout all phases:

- (i) *Dynamic goal and scope* (e.g., changes in service life over time),
- (ii) *Dynamic inventory analysis* (e.g., time-dependent variations in foreground and background systems),
- (iii) *Dynamic impact assessment* (e.g., temporally differentiated characterization factors), and
- (iv) *Dynamic interpretation* (e.g., time-sensitive weighting factors).

In contrast, a partial dynamic LCA incorporates temporal variation only in selected phases or components, such as applying time differentiation solely to the foreground inventory. However, such partial applications can lead to inconsistencies—for example, using a dynamic inventory without matching temporal resolution in the characterization phase, or modelling time-variant foreground processes without considering changes in background systems. These mismatches may undermine the validity of the results and lead to misleading conclusions.

One key aspect of DLCA is *dynamic characterization*, where characterization factors are adjusted to reflect the timing of emissions or resource use—such as accounting for the difference in climate impact of CO₂ released today versus in the future. This is particularly relevant for product systems involving biogenic carbon from sources with long regrowth periods, like wood (Guest & Strømman, 2014).

Despite their importance, dynamic LCIA methods are not yet widely supported in mainstream LCA software. Advancements in modelling tools are essential to enable more robust and structured implementations of time-sensitive assessments. Open-source platforms like Brightway, a Python-based LCA framework (Mutel, 2017), pioneering progress in this area, laying the groundwork for broader adoption of fully dynamic LCA methodologies. Yet, a full dynamic life cycle inventory has only been realized by the DyPLCA framework, tool and database. The latest version of the DyPLCA database contains temporal parameter data for all ecoinvent 3.11 processes. Improvements were made in deliverable 2.1 of LCA4BIO (Schaubroeck et al., 2025), focusing on dynamic carbon footprint, improving as well dynamic climate change CF.

LCIA is inherently complex, involving assumptions—such as future environmental conditions—that can limit the temporal validity of results and introduce biases. One of the most common temporal elements in LCIA is the time horizon (TH), which defines the assessment period. For instance, the ReCiPe method uses three cultural perspectives (individualist, hierarchist, egalitarian), each applying different THs (e.g., 20, 100, or 1000 years) and corresponding assumptions for impact categories like global warming potential (GWP).

Other ways time is considered in LCIA methods include (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020):

- **Period of validity:** Although rarely stated, indicating the applicable time range of an LCIA method (e.g., 2000–2010) can clarify its temporal relevance.
- **Short- vs long-term analysis:** Differentiating between immediate and future impacts.
- **Period-specific characterization factors:** Dynamic LCIA (DLCIA) methods have been developed, especially for GWP and toxicity, to apply time-sensitive CFs that reflect the timing of emissions.
- **Non-linear mechanisms:** DLCIA methods must also address complex, time-dependent environmental processes influenced by physical, chemical, and biological dynamics, which interact in non-linear ways, e.g. as done by Arbault et al. (2014).

Overall, while dynamic approaches have advanced, their application is still limited and mainly focused on specific impact categories. Climate change is the most extensively studied impact category regarding time considerations in LCIA. Early efforts addressed the limitations of fixed time horizons by introducing characterization factors (CFs) for 20, 100, and 500 years, which are still commonly used in LCA databases. (Cherubini, Peters, et al., 2011), proposed a dynamic method based on radiative forcing, combining CO₂ decay and biomass uptake rates, while others (Levasseur et al., 2010) and (Kendall, 2012) introduced time-dependent CFs calculated annually, preserving the conventional LCA framework but requiring a large number of CFs. In the toxicity category, CFs for 20, 100, and 500 years were calculated using the USES-LCA model for policy relevance. Similarly, (Lebailly et al., 2014) applied the USEtox® model to compute CFs for each year post-emission, improving temporal resolution in toxicity assessments.

4.2 Dynamic model for toxicity

4.2.1 Model presentation

The dynamic model for toxicity impact, named “DyTox” was developed by INSA/TBI in the framework of a past research project funded by ANR France and FNR Luxembourg, DyPLCA (Dynamic process life cycle assessment), in which INSA/TBI and LIST were partners.

This model combines the three parts of the toxicity impact: pollutant fate, exposure and effect. It considers that the fate of the pollutant is the limiting dynamic process because it can be slow. The temporality of the impact is thus dependent on the temporality of the pollutant fate in the environment. To model the fate process dynamics, the SimpleBox conceptual model was used. It considers each environmental compartment as a homogenous box, and the pollutant is exchanged between each pair of boxes with a specific “velocity”. More details on the model structure and the developed software are available in respective work (Shimako et al., 2017). Actually, DyTox is based on 13 environmental compartments, which ensures its compatibility with the existent methods and data bases, notably USEtox.

4.2.2 Data used in the model

The model is applicable with any data structured following the USEtox database. DyTox was initially used with the USEtox database for inorganic and organic substances. It was completed in the frame of LCA4BIO with the data from Environmental Footprint (EF) method for toxicity and ecotoxicity impacts, which is also recommended in the previous section 3. It is now operational with both databases.

4.3 Bibliographic review in other categories: Dynamic and prospective models

This literature review is not intended as an exhaustive study but rather as a representation of the state of the art to investigate the integration of temporal dynamics aspects in LCIA methods for land use, water use, biodiversity and ecosystem services.

4.3.1 Land Use change

Integrating temporal aspects into the LUC category in LCA is essential for accurately capturing the time-dependent effects of human interventions on ecosystems, carbon dynamics, and ES. Conventional LCA typically lacks temporal resolution, assuming static impacts. However, land use and its changes are dynamic by nature, involving transitions, recovery periods, and long-term consequences. Temporal aspects in LUC include: (i) Land transformation (conversion from one use to another) causes immediate impacts (e.g., habitat loss, carbon release), (ii) Land occupation (continuous use) causes ongoing impacts (e.g., degradation, erosion, reduced biodiversity), (iii) Recovery processes (e.g., reforestation, soil regeneration) occur over years to decades, (iv)

Carbon and biodiversity impacts of LUC are not linear and are influenced by the duration and nature of land use transitions.

In the LUC impact category, THs are typically not explicitly defined in existing characterization models. Instead, these models often operate under the assumption of an infinite time horizon, whereby the impacts of land use interventions are integrated over time until the effect factor declines to zero. This point is reached when the affected soil quality fully regenerates to its reference condition. Consequently, regeneration time plays a critical role in determining both the effective integration period and the derivation of CFs (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020).

Several methodological strategies have been proposed to improve the temporal realism of LUC impact assessments in LCA, such as carbon flows, scenario-based modelling, time-scale alignment, and biodiversity-recovery timelines.

Dynamic carbon modelling acknowledges that carbon emissions and removals occur over time, especially in sectors like forestry, agriculture, and bio-based systems. Studies have applied dynamic LCA frameworks that track annual emissions, delayed emissions, and carbon sequestration (Cherubini et al., 2012; Cherubini, Strømman, et al., 2011). Models such as IPCC Tier 2/3 methodologies estimate net carbon balances over defined periods (e.g., 20, 50, or 100 years) (Borgen et al., 2012; Pilli et al., 2015). Improvements were made in deliverable 2.1 of LCA4BIO (Schaubroeck et al., 2025), focusing on dynamic carbon footprint, improving as well dynamic climate change CF.

Temporal integration can also be achieved by simulating LUC trajectories or scenario-based transitions, such as deforestation followed by reforestation or urban expansion followed by ecological restoration. Tools like GLOBIOM, IMAGE, and LUCI are commonly used to simulate land-use changes across different spatial and temporal scales (Alexander et al., 2017; De Rosa et al., 2016).

Some LCA studies apply explicit time horizons (e.g., 100 years) to align the time scale of impacts from land occupation and subsequent recovery (Müller-Wenk & Brandão, 2010; Schmidt et al., 2015). Others utilize time-resolved inventory data, such as annual land occupation or emission data, instead of cumulative or average flows. These datasets can then be used in dynamic LCIA models that calculate impact intensities per year or across time slices (Levasseur et al., 2010).

Biodiversity impacts of LUC can also be assessed over time by incorporating the duration of land occupation and the recovery period. Metrics such as time-integrated species loss or Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) over time are used to reflect the delayed recovery of ecosystems (e.g., in secondary forests). Dynamic CFs can be developed to represent biodiversity trajectories during ecosystem recovery (Curran et al., 2011; De Baan et al., 2013).

4.3.2 Water Use

Water use is a key concern in bio-based systems, particularly due to the demands of biomass cultivation. While process industries also contribute to water use, their impact is generally lower. With the expected increase in agricultural and forest biomass production, overall water consumption is likely to rise (Pawelzik et al., 2013).

In LCIA, standard water scarcity characterization methods are predominantly spatially explicit, accounting for geographic variations in water availability and demand, but not temporally resolved. Most traditional methods, such as (Pfister et al., 2009) and the original AWARE method, do not include changes over time, like seasonal variations or future projections. However, there is growing interest in integrating temporal dynamics into LCIA water scarcity assessments to improve accuracy and regional relevance.

Recent developments in the field are beginning to address this gap. Temporal aspects being considered include:

- Seasonal differences (e.g., wet vs. dry seasons)
- Monthly or daily water stress patterns

- Time-varying water consumption and availability

Some extensions of the AWARE model now include monthly water scarcity characterization factors, allowing for finer temporal resolution. A significant advancement came from the WULCA (Water Use in Life Cycle Assessment) working group of the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, which developed the AWARE method. This regionalized LCIA method is based on the "availability minus demand" (AMD) principle and was designed to reflect water scarcity in a globally consistent and spatially differentiated way. The original AWARE method used data from the WaterGAP2.2 model for water availability and demand inputs. Research by (Lee et al., 2018) and (Boulay et al., 2018) explore dynamic modelling approaches that incorporate temporal variability in water flows and use in AWARE model.

Looking ahead, (Pfister et al., 2011) made one of the first efforts to integrate future projections (i.e., prospective CFs) of water scarcity by using climate change scenarios along with the WaterGAP 2 model, resulting in prospective CF. More recently, (Baustert et al., 2022) extended this work by incorporating future scenarios into the AWARE methodology, providing a new batch of prospective water use CF. In their study, water scarcity characterization factors were projected for the period 2010–2050, using results from the SSP-RCP scenario framework (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and Representative Concentration Pathways) as modelled by the IMAGE integrated assessment model.

The IMAGE model provided a range of temporal and spatial data, including:

- Monthly discharge (hm^3/day) representing net water availability
- Monthly irrigation and water use (mm/month and l/month), together representing human water consumption (HWC)
- Natural water discharge over time

Water availability and flows were calculated for 1950–2010, with human water consumption estimated for 2010. While Pfister et al. (2011) remain the only study projecting LCIA characterization factors into the future while maintaining a static life cycle inventory (LCI) background, Baustert et al. (2022) show how dynamic and prospective data and integrated scenarios can push the field forward.

In conclusion, while traditional LCIA methods for water scarcity are largely static and spatial, the field is evolving to incorporate temporal variability and future scenario modelling, which will be critical for assessing the sustainability of water use in a changing climate.

4.3.3 Ecosystem services

The integration of ES into LCA has gained significant attention to capture a broader and more ecologically relevant range of environmental impacts, particularly those related to land use, biodiversity, and long-term ecosystem functioning. ES, such as carbon sequestration, water purification, pollination, soil fertility, and habitat provision, represent the essential benefits humans derive from natural ecosystems. Including these services in LCA supports a more comprehensive sustainability assessment by linking human activities with ecosystem functions and benefit (Verones et al., 2020).

Despite growing recognition of society's dependence on ES, current LCIA methods often fall short of explicitly and fully quantifying the damage caused by human activities on the generation and maintenance of these services. Recent advances in LCIA have begun to address this gap by focusing on specific cause–effect chains, especially those related to land use changes, which have led to the development of CFs at the midpoint level aimed at capturing ecosystem service potentials.

Traditionally, LCA has emphasized midpoint and endpoint indicators related to emissions, resource depletion, and land occupation, frequently neglecting the complex and dynamic nature of ecosystems and the services they provide. Current approaches for integrating ES into LCA can be broadly categorized into three main strategies:

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- Midpoint-based approaches use biophysical indicators such as soil organic carbon (SOC), net primary productivity, or species richness as proxies to approximate the impacts of activities on ecosystem services (De Baan et al., 2013). Recent research has focused on linking elementary flows in the life cycle inventory (e.g., land occupation and land transformation) to novel midpoint impact categories termed 'potential damage on Ecosystem Services' (Koellner & Geyer, 2013). Spatially differentiated CFs have been developed to assess specific ES-related impacts, including biodiversity damage (de Baan et al., 2013), climate regulation (Müller-Wenk & Brandão, 2010), biotic production (Brandão & I Canals, 2013), erosion control, freshwater regulation, water purification (Saad et al., 2013), and groundwater water supply (Zelm et al., 2011).
- Endpoint-based approaches attempt to quantify changes in ecosystem services in terms of human well-being or economic value, often using monetary valuation techniques or health-related metrics such as DALYs (Müller-Wenk & Brandão, 2010). These approaches aim to translate ecosystem damages into impacts on human health and welfare but face challenges in valuation consistency and uncertainty.
- Hybrid approaches combine LCA with spatially explicit ecosystem service models such as InVEST, ARIES, GLOBIO, and IMAGE to assess ecosystem service impacts more comprehensively and incorporate them within the LCA framework (Boulay et al., 2018). These models provide geospatially detailed outputs on ES flows and can address ecosystem complexity better than purely inventory-based methods.

A major challenge in integrating ES into LCA is the treatment of temporal dynamics. Conventional LCA approaches generally assume temporal homogeneity and apply characterization factors without temporal differentiation (VanderWilde & Newell, 2021). However, ES are inherently dynamic, varying over time due to seasonal fluctuations, land-use changes, climate variability, and other ecological processes. Managing temporal variability is essential to produce realistic and policy-relevant LCA results that can inform long-term sustainability decisions. Several strategies have been proposed to incorporate temporal dimensions in ES modelling for LCA:

- Time horizon alignment: While LCIA commonly uses fixed timeframes (e.g., 100 years for global warming potential), ecosystem models simulate dynamics on seasonal, annual, or multi-decadal scales. Harmonization can be achieved by averaging ES flows over specified periods or adjusting results to align with the temporal scope of LCA assessments (Lueddeckens et al., 2020)
- Scenario-based modeling: Integrating scenarios such as Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) enables projection of ES provision under alternative socio-environmental futures. These scenarios, when combined with integrated assessment models (e.g., IMAGE, WaterGAP), provide dynamic inputs that improve temporal resolution in LCA (Baustert et al., 2022).
- Use of dynamic models: Spatially explicit ecosystem service tools like InVEST and ARIES generate time-resolved outputs (e.g., annual carbon sequestration, seasonal water flow regulation) that can be integrated into the LCI or LCIA phases. Such dynamic outputs enable better representation of temporal fluctuations in ecosystem functions.
- Discounting or time-weighting: Temporal variation in ecosystem service provision can also be managed through economic or social discounting methods, though this approach raises ethical questions about the valuation of future ecosystem benefits and intergenerational equity (Müller-Wenk & Brandão, 2010).

Several studies have demonstrated the feasibility and value of incorporating prospective ecosystem service modelling within LCA. For example, (Pfister et al., 2011) used the WaterGAP model to project future water stress indices under climate change scenarios. As discussed previously in section 4.3.2, (Baustert et al., 2022) applied SSP-RCP scenarios within the AWARE water scarcity method, projecting water scarcity characterization factors from 2010 to 2050 using outputs from the IMAGE model. These studies utilized detailed hydrological

and socio-economic datasets, including monthly discharge, irrigation demands, and natural water flows, to develop temporally LCIA indicators. Advancing this concept, (Arbault et al., 2014) explored the use of integrated earth system dynamic modelling to derive time- and scenario-dependent characterization factors that reflect the complex interactions between natural processes delivering ecosystem services. They employed the GUMBO (Global Unified Metamodel of the Biosphere) model to quantify changes in ecosystem service production in biophysical terms at the midpoint level and corresponding changes in human welfare indicators at the endpoint level.

4.3.4 Biodiversity

Integrating temporal aspects into biodiversity impact assessment in LCA remains a methodological challenge but is essential for capturing the dynamic nature of ecological responses. As discussed in the previous sections, traditional LCIA methods are typically static and do not explicitly account for the time. However, if we include temporal aspects on the five main drivers of biodiversity loss (habitat loss and degradation, climate change, pollution, overexploitation and invasive species) (Winter et al., 2017), the dynamic aspects could be integrated in biodiversity impact, e.g., duration of land use or emissions. Recent advances have introduced dynamic approaches that consider factors such as land use duration, time-lagged biodiversity loss (e.g., extinction debt), ecosystem recovery times (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Curran et al., 2011) and climate change (Iordan et al., 2023).

For instance, (Chaudhary et al., 2015; Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019) developed global CFs that incorporate the duration of land occupation and distinguish between temporary and permanent land use impacts. Dynamic models based on species–area relationships and land-use trajectories further allow the estimation of biodiversity loss over time, accounting for delayed ecosystem responses (De Baan et al., 2013; Koellner & Geyer, 2013). Despite these advances, the integration of temporal dimensions is still limited by high data demands, spatial variability, and uncertainties in ecological recovery processes. As a result, best practices encourage the use of temporally differentiated models where available and the inclusion of sensitivity analyses to explore the implications of time-related assumptions in biodiversity impacts.

4.4 Bio based chemical tested in Toxicity dynamic model

This section shows the evaluation of the toxicity model described in section 4.2 for bio-based chemicals. The objective is calculating the time depending on impacts of ecotoxicity and human toxicity within LCA. This model includes dynamic impact assessment, with focus on a dynamic fate model for the bio-based chemicals in the environment, combined with the EF model for toxicity assessment. A list of seven bio-based chemicals (**Table 17**) were selected based on their importance in the global market, i.e., global production capacity (IEA Bioenergy, 2020) and inclusion of EF 3.1 method (See EF 3.1 database here: [EF 3.1](#)).

Table 17. List of bio-based chemicals evaluated by Dynamic toxicity model

Chemical	Formula	Global Capacity (kta) year 2020*	CAS no	Description*
Ethylene	C ₂ H ₄	200	74-85-1	Ethylene is used to make common plastics, and its global production grew from 150 to 175 million tonnes (2016–2021). It can be made from bioethanol or bionaphtha, both from renewable sources. Bioethanol, mainly produced by the USA and Brazil, converts to ethylene with over 99% efficiency at 400°C. Large ethylene plants use large amounts of ethanol.
Ethanol	C ₂ H ₆ O	80,800	64-17-5	Ethanol is the most established biobased chemical, mainly used for transportation fuels. Significant amounts are also used to produce biobased ethylene, ethylene oxide, and MEG. The ethanol market is dominated by the USA and Brazil.

Glycerol	$C_3H_8O_3$	1,500	56-81-5	Glycerol is a clear, odorless, sweet-tasting liquid commonly used as a moisturizer, sweetener, and solvent. It's a key ingredient in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, food products, and industrial applications due to its non-toxic and hygroscopic properties.
Lactic acid	$C_3H_6O_3$	>600	50-21-5	Lactic acid is widely used in food, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, textiles and personal care for its preservative, solvent, and skin benefits. Its fastest growth is in bio-based polymers, especially polylactic acid (PLA), a biodegradable plastic used in packaging, mulch films, and bags. European PLA demand is 25,000 tonnes annually, potentially rising to 650,000 tonnes by 2025.
Furfural	$C_5H_4O_2$	360	98-01-1	Furfural, made by dehydrating five-carbon sugars, is part of the furanics chemical group. It is mainly used to produce furfuryl alcohol. Production is declining in developed countries but rising in developing ones, with China as the top producer using corn cobs.
Citric acid	$C_6H_8O_7$	2,000	77-92-9	It is the largest chemical produced through biomass fermentation and the most commonly used organic acid. Citric acid serves multiple roles such as acidulant, preservative, emulsifier, flavor enhancer, chelating, and buffering agent, with broad applications in food, beverage, pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and cosmetic industries.
HMF	$C_6H_6O_3$	-	67-47-0	HMF (5-Hydroxymethylfurfural) is an organic compound formed by the dehydration of sugars. It's an important platform chemical used in biofuel production, polymers, and as a precursor for various chemicals.

*Source: (IEA Bioenergy, 2020)

This section is structured in two sub-sections: first, the dynamic fate of the bio-based chemical in different environment compartments and the second part focuses on the dynamic toxicity impacts (ecotoxicity and human toxicity) at midpoint level.

4.4.1 Dynamic fate modelling for bio-based chemicals

To calculate dynamic toxicity, the first step is to calculate the fate of the bio-based chemicals. **Figure 7** shows the mass of ethylene in the air compartment for 8 years, while for the rest of bio-based chemicals were assumed to be emitted into water compartment for 8 years (except for lactic acid, evaluated over 80 years). For each bio-based chemical, an emission of 1 kg was considered as a pulse (year 0) in the water, soil or air compartment.

Figure 7 highlights the mass of the bio-based chemicals evaluated that drops considerably before second year after emission. Ethylene disappears around year 1, while HMF after 2 years. These results demonstrate that these components are non-persistent in these compartments. This mass decreasing in all compartments entails no accumulation and faster transfer and removal processes. The fast depletion can be usually explained by kinetics of removal and degradation rates with a high order of magnitude (Shimako et al., 2017). A different fate profile is obtained in the case of lactic acid, which requires around 30 years to drop to total depletion, which describes a more persistent substance in comparison to other bio-based chemicals.

Figure 7. Bio-based chemical fate over 8 years (in case of Lactic acid, over 80 years): Ethylene (A), Ethanol (B), Glycerol (C), Lactic acid (D), Furfural (E), Citric acid (F) and HMF (G)

For comparison, **Figure 8** illustrates the fate profile of furfural released into two different compartments: water and soil. The results indicate similar behavior, with an environmental persistence of approximately one year. However, depletion in the water compartment is slightly greater than in the soil after one year, but a more detailed discussion would require graphs with monthly resolution.

Figure 8. Furfural fate in environment over 8 years for water compartment (A) and soil compartment (B).

4.4.2 Dynamic toxicity modelling for bio-based chemicals

Figure 9A and **Figure 9B** show the shapes for ecotoxicity for ethylene and HMF. These components were selected as example, but the same ecotoxicity behavior was obtained in all the bio-based chemicals evaluated. The ecotoxicity curves similarity for all the bio-based chemicals evaluated can be explained by the similar shape obtained for the mass in the fate calculation. The ecotoxicity model used considers only the fate step in a dynamic manner, while exposure and effect steps are independent of time, i.e., considered as constant values. The ecotoxicity impact drops drastically after the emission, represented as a peak in the year 0, which implies that a ecotoxicity impact occurs in the first moment after emission and then the impact disappears.

In the case of human toxicity impacts (**Figure 9C** and **Figure 9D**), in these graphs cancer and non-cancer effects are analyzed for ethylene emitted to air and HMF emitted to water as examples. For all the bio-based chemicals emitted to water the cancer and non-cancer effects remain in zero (no toxic), but for ethylene emitted to air (See **Figure 7A**) and Furfural emitted to soil (See **Figure 8B**) there is a non-persistent non-cancer effect in the immediate moment after emission, which is described for a peak in the non-cancer effect in **Figure 9C**.

Figure 9. Dynamic toxicity calculated for 8 years for Ethylene emitted to air, ecotoxicity (A), HMF emitted to water, ecotoxicity (B), Ethylene emitted to air, human toxicity cancer and non-cancer effects (C), and HMF emitted to water, human toxicity cancer and non-cancer effect (D).

4.5 Supplementary Information: Set of prospective/dynamic CFs or models

A set of temporal considerations in LCIA methods are detailed in **Supplementary Information Part 3**. Temporal differentiation for toxicity was examined using a dynamic modeling approach applied to seven representative bio-based chemicals, following the methodology developed by INSA (Shimako et al., 2017). This model assesses how human toxicity and ecotoxicity characterization factors evolve over time. For other LCIA impact categories, biodiversity and water use, CFs are compiled based on selected example studies. Supplementary Information Part 3 is divided into the following sections: Section 1 (S1): List of evaluated bio-based chemicals; Section 2 (S2): Toxicity; Section 3 (S3): Biodiversity; Section 4 (S4): Water Use and Section.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The growing number of LCIA methods in LCA presents significant challenges that hinder consistency, transparency, and effective decision-making. These methods often rely on different impact pathways, characterization models, and assumptions, which can lead to inconsistent results for the same product system and complicate cross-study comparisons. This methodological diversity can be overwhelming for practitioners, who may struggle to identify the most appropriate method for their specific context or system boundaries.

This document aims to address these challenges by promoting a harmonized approach based on a comparative analysis of the most widely used LCIA methods. The focus is on impact categories especially relevant to bio-based systems, such as toxicity, land use, water use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. Our work builds upon ongoing efforts in LCA research and coordination projects, such as CALIMERO and ALIGNED, which aim to align and improve LCA practices across the bioeconomy. Using a defined set of criteria and a scoring system, we have identified the most promising LCIA methods for assessing environmental impacts in bio-based systems, according to our insights, with particular attention to their applicability and scientific robustness.

In addition, this document emphasizes the importance of integrating temporal and dynamic aspects into LCIA, which is particularly critical for bio-based systems. These systems are inherently time-sensitive due to biological growth cycles, carbon sequestration dynamics, and long-term land use implications. Incorporating time explicitly in LCIA allows for a more accurate and realistic representation of environmental impacts, particularly for ecosystem degradation, and delayed toxicity effects. In this context, we have conducted a dynamic assessment of toxicity impacts for a selected group of bio-based chemicals and performed a comprehensive literature review to capture recent advances in the integration of temporal aspects in LCIA methods related to land use, water use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services.

Ultimately, we hope this document can serve as a practical guide for LCIA method selection in future LCA studies of bio-based systems. Moreover, by highlighting current gaps in the temporal and dynamic integration within LCIA, we aim to support future methodological developments and research efforts toward more comprehensive and time-explicit sustainability assessments.

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